
**PHYTOREMEDIATION CHARACTERISTICS: TAILING WASTE
REHABILITATION AT OK TEDI MINING LIMITED, WESTERN PROVINCE
PAPUA NEW GUINEA**

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Statement of Originality

I, Nathaniel Dasyal, hereby declare that the work presented herein is original work done by me and has not been published or submitted elsewhere for the requirement of a Master's Degree programme. Any literature date or work done by others and cited within this thesis has been given due acknowledgement, and listed in the reference section.

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Abstract

In latest years, researchers and engineers have begun to develop low-cost technologies and mechanisms, such as purifying contaminated areas with microorganisms / biomass and live plants. Of these, phytoremediation mechanisms are emerging and are promising green mechanisms that can be used to remediate heavy metal contaminated soils through various means such as phytoremediation, phytostabilisation, phytovolatilization and rhizofiltration. Decontamination of contaminants warrant various choices and strategies in phytoremediation, and include soil properties, heavy metal levels and characteristics, plant species, and climate. Heavy metals like Cd, Pb, Hg, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cr, and Co are non-essential metals. Many of them are highly toxic both in elemental and soluble salt forms. The phytoremediation mechanisms that were used in this study were phytoextraction, phytostabilisation and phytomobilization (phytoaccumulation); as these are cost effective, and have aesthetic advantages and long-term applicability. Certain species of plants especially; shrubs, primary trees, secondary trees, weeds and grasses were studied because of their tolerance for high heavy metal levels in trials with tailing dumps in OK Tedi, in Papua New Guinea (PNG). The challenge in the study was aimed at investigating plant species that have phytoremedial characteristics by possessing the attributes of exceptionally high metal- accumulating capacity or are hyper accumulators, having roots possessing unique and selective capability to absorb, have entire structures that can translocate bio accumulate and degrade the heavy metals, plants according to evidence have large above ground biomass and also possess extensive shallow rooting systems and having the ability to take up both essential and non-essential heavy metals. This study revealed that several plant species such as white clover and typha can withstand heavy metal concentration whilst other species tend to decline over time. The investigation indicated high mortality rates from homalantus, kikuyu, trema and lupin, compared with struggle and survival rates demonstrated by Typha, White Clover and Tephrosia in the high concentrated tailing stored divans. Heavy metals that were not too concentrated were zinc, copper and cadmium, whilst lead and nickel were highly concentrated, and so plants did not seem to tolerate their presence in large quantities.

The main factors that influenced morphology of plant species were plant spacing and growth medium, tailings chemistry in terms of different interactions and reactions due to their different characteristics and concentration levels, weather conditions through wet and dry patterns and periods along with the plants natural ability to acclimatize.

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Historical Background

The use of plants to remediate toxic chemicals found in contaminated soil, sludge, sediments, ground water, surface water and waste water. Phytoremediation technology has various essential processes for metal extraction and dilution for organic and inorganic contaminants such as phyto – transformation or degradation, rhizo-filtration and rhizo – degradation and phyto – stabilization and phyto – extraction respectively Tangahu.; Abdullah.; Basri.; Idris.; Anar., Mukhlisim., 2011 & Ahman, I., Larsson S;1994.

Bioavailability is defeated through fluid filtration by plants which compacts contaminants in the growth medium. These all is called the phytostabilization process. Accumulation, absorption, adsorption or hail in and onto the root parameters can restrict contaminants in some plant species especially with soils, sediments and sludge infested with heavy metals contaminants. Specific plant species can absorb and hyper-accumulate metal contaminants and or excess nutrients in harvestable roots and shoots tissues from the growth substrate through phytoextraction process. In various conditions for metals, metalloids, radionuclides, non – metals and organic contaminants.

Phytovolatilization process is the plants ability to absorb and subsequently volatilize the contaminants into the atmosphere. This process is for metal contaminants in groundwater, soil, sediments and sludge medium. The processes of contaminant metabolism and degradation called phyto-transformation and phyto – degradation by plants generate and give off interactive compounds. This process is for complex organic molecules that are degraded into simpler contaminant molecule(s) in soils, sediments, sludge, and groundwater medium.

Copious nutrients and heavy metal contaminants are taken up to the plant parts through the roots through rhizofiltration especially through adsorption and precipitation attachments to the roots or into the contaminants roots parameters through a solution purposely for surplus nutrients, underground, above ground and or excess water contaminant radionuclides.

Conductive root zones or rhizo – degradation instigate favourable conditions of microbial activities for metabolism and conversion of contaminants into organic constituents for energy and nutrients. Metabolism. Natural substance(s) released by the plant roots, sugar, alcohol and acids contain organic carbon that provides food for soil microorganisms and establish a dense root mass that takes up large quantities of water. This process is for organic contaminants in soil medium.

Phytoremediation trialled out in various contaminated sites to mitigate environmental impacts showed costly with no difference and change in any condition. The chemical technologies that are employed generate large volumetric sludge and increase the costs; chemical and thermal methods are both technically difficult and expensive as all of these methods can also degrade the valuable components of the soils. Conventionally, remediation of soils contaminated with heavy metals involves either onsite management, or excavation and subsequent disposal to a landfill site which causes more impacts and pollution from relocation of contaminants from place to place. Furnace and straining and filtering also mitigates high concentration levels of contaminants as an alternative. However, this method too is costly and produces a residual rich in heavy metals which will require further treatment. Moreover, the physico-chemical technologies used for soil remediation render the land usage as a medium for plant growth untenable, as they remove all biological activities. The chemical technologies that are employed generate large volumetric sludge and increase the costs; chemical and thermal methods are both technically difficult and expensive as all of these methods can also degrade the valuable components of the soils. Conventionally, remediation of soils contaminated with heavy metals involves either onsite management, or excavation and subsequent disposal to a landfill site.

Soil washing for removing contaminated soil is an alternative way to excavation and disposal to landfills. However, this method too is costly and produces a residual rich in heavy metals which will require further treatment. Moreover, the physico-chemical technologies used for soil remediation render the land usage as a medium for plant growth untenable, as they remove all biological activities.

Many species of plants have been successfully used in absorbing contaminants such as lead, cadmium, chromium, arsenic and various radionuclides from soils [International Journal of Chemical Engineering, August 2011]. One of the phytoremediation categories, phyto-extraction, can be used to remove heavy metals from the soils using its ability to take up metals

which are essential for plant growth (Fe, Mn, Cu, Mg, Mo and Ni). Accumulation can also occur from metals with scarce biological aspects. Heavy metals are conservatively defined as elements with relatively high densities, atomic numbers and weights. The most common heavy metal contaminants are; Cd, Cr, Cu, Hg, Pb and Zn, but it is also important to mention that metals are natural components in soil and for plant morphology in terms of growth and development. Contaminated medium infested with heavy metals have high detrimental potential on biological ecosystem with slow biodegradation however adaptability and susceptibility differs in all organisms. Those that don't withstand accumulate in their tissues causing various diseases and disorders, even in relatively low concentration. Heavy metals enclosed and housed with dirt for so many years are threat to many species and organisms. They are also known to have effects on plants growth, ground cover, and have negative impact on soil microflora. They are also known to have effects on plants growth, ground cover, and have negative impact on soil microflora.

1.2. Problem Statement

It is postulated that operational activities over the years at OK Tedi mining may deteriorate the ecosystem with toxic heavy metals. Presence of soluble segments of metals in soil solutions or those that are easily filtered and absorbed by plants as heavy metals are required for morphology. However uptake of too much can have detrimental effects on the plants. Essential and non-essential are accommodated and taken up as plant nutrients for growth and development again as mentioned that excessive accumulation directly or indirectly and potentially affect the plant species.

Cytoplasmic enzymes that are responsible for holding and protecting cells can be harmed from toxic effects caused by heavy concentrated metals through oxidative stress. Cation exchangeable areas of plants for essential nutrients is an example of indirect contamination effect. Opposing impact of heavy metals surplus or inadequacy can instigate poor morphological changes and undesired microbial activities indirectly as well. Also beneficial soil microorganisms can underperform functions required of them to maintain balance given intolerable and excessive concentration levels of heavy metals that are toxic. Heavy metal interaction and interference with microorganisms in the soil can reduce chemical reactions and reduce plant growth and development over time. Toxic conditions morphology directly and indirectly in all circumstances

Heavy metals can cause oxidative stress (Mudilapi et al., 2008) by forming free radicals. Oxidative stress refers to the situation in the cells of an organism, especially animals, whereby there is an increase in the number of reactive oxygen species which can overwhelm cell's intrinsic antioxidants defences and can lead to cell damage or death. Regarding their toxicities, the most problematic heavy metals are, Hg, Cd, and Pb, As, Cu, Zn, Sn and Cr (Wright, 2007; Ghosh, 2010). In this study, seven species of plants currently used by the Environment Management Team for their rehabilitation program on the exposed areas and contaminated sites within the mine area (including the tailing dam) were used. These species were selected based on their adaptive modes of being found growing in high altitude ranging from low to upper montane and also possessing shallow rooting systems. However, their use for phytoremediation in heavily contaminated areas such as the tailing waste is a challenge which this study is aimed at investigating.

1.3. Objectives

- To evaluate the potential of phytoremediation technique for the treatment of heavy metal-contaminated sites, and to describe the fate of heavy metals in plant tissue
- To identify plant species best adapted for uptake of tailings contaminants.
- To demonstrate that plant-based clean-up is conducive with less cost and less environmental impacts.

1.4. Limitation of Study

The flaws and shortcomings experienced from the study are;

- Labour availability for consistent field data collection.
- Heavy rainfall area causing disturbance in plot maintenance and data collection
- Unavailability of financial support leading to lowering of the scope of the study, such as; limited coverage area for the study, less trials, and reduced sample analyses parameters for monitoring and analyses.

1.5. Hypothesis

The plant species; *Tephrosia vogelii* (a leguminous shrub), Lupin (a shrub), Trema (secondary tree), Homalanthus (secondary tree), Typha, Pennisetum and *Trifolium repens*, have tremendous potential for tailing waste rehabilitation, and may have phytoremediation

characteristics. Other plants that were included were *Poa keysseri*, *Polygonum spp.*, *Imperata cylindrical*, *Erigeron*

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Definition of Phytoremediation

Phytoremediation route involves in-situ absorption, degradation and containment of hazardous contaminants in sediment infested soils, surface water and ground water via the use of plants. The different types of Phytoremediation are;

Phytostabilization occurs when chemical compounds produced by plants immobilize contaminants instead of degrading them

Phyto – or phytoextraction, is the process by which chemical compounds produced by the roots bind with toxins and water along with other nutrients. The toxins do not get destroyed but end up in the leaves of plants.

Phyto – volatilization - refers to the process in which plants absorb organic contaminants from their surroundings and release the contaminants into the atmosphere via their greeneries.

There are many reasons for initiating and implementing phytoremediation, such as observation of plants growing in concentrated and contaminated areas, reduced cost, less harmful method, preserves top soil and reduces erosion, and can be monitored easily.

In the world of science and technology, phytoremediation comes in different forms. Globalization has posed problems in environmental protection and conservation (Bennett et al., 2003). The demand for economic growth often outweighs the need for environmental protection. Often, the demand for economic development outweighs the need for environmental safety, yet economic and industrial developments impact environmental safety (Ikhuoria & Okiemen, 2000).

There are various methods for repairing metal-contaminated soil (Ebbs and Kochian., 1997), ranging from physical, thermal and chemical methods to biological methods. Physical methods include soil replacement, surface covering, landfill, and encapsulation. Chemical methods include soil flushing, immobilization, soil cleaning and solidification, thermal and electrical methods target electrokinetics and vitrification, and this research is bioremediation and phytoremediation process which is all about re-establishment. Focused on promoting the establishment and re-establishment of plants on contaminated soils and growth media that are considered environmentally friendly and economical (Weyens., N., van der Lelle., D., Taghavi, S. , Vangronsveld, J., 2009b).

2.2. Metal Tolerance in Trees

Contaminated soil, surface and groundwater around the world are affected by large-scale industrial activities due to ignorance and negligence, lack of vision, and high costs of waste treatment and treatment. The major constraints and strains to the ecosystem, soil, surface and ground water are mostly affected by heavy metals, radionuclide and organic contaminants. Phytoremediation in the recent years is considered to be environmental contamination solution. Tolerant plants have been utilized to mitigate toxic organic and compounds from the soil, surface and ground water through the green technology approach. Phytoremediation encompasses growing of plants in contaminated medium to extract and remove environmental contaminants through the sequestration and degradation and or detoxification processes of the filths. The ability of plants to metabolize, absorb and transport is unique given the practice of nutrient uptake and the systematic selection of pollutants within the limits of consumption from growing media, surface and / or ground water.

Irrespective of benefits, influential factors such as cost and climatic conditions can impede speed, comparability and plant growth compared to traditional methods that are physical and chemical treatments of bio-remediation. Phytoremediation can restore balance to the stressed environment at less cost but public opposition to phytoremediation could be a issue. It is important to mitigate environmental contamination with caution through use of green plant technology. The success of green technology is dependent on several influential factors. Firstly the species must produce adequate biomass whilst high concentrated metal are being accumulated whilst in some cases increased biomass will lower the total concentration of the metals in the plant vessels but shall allow for a larger amount of metals to be accumulated in general Secondly the metal accumulating plants need to be adherent to different industrial conditions practices for establishment and re establishment, absorption and neutralisation of metal rich vessels and components. Hence it is better for metal accumulation in the shoots than the roots so that the metals in the shoots can be chopped off and eradicated. This can be practical on small small operation but is impractical in bigger industries. The entire plant can be removed if the metals are concentrated in the roots. However the need for full plant removal maybe costly with added manpower and planting which takes time to plant, establish new plants and start accumulating metal.

On the other hand, heavy metal are harmful and are the contributing factor to plant growth and development (Mullins., 1991) Concentrated heavy metals are lethal and cause increased mortality in plants and other living organisms. However there plant spesces than can withstand heavy metal concentration and maintain growth and development regardless of the concnetration levels. Retreated heavy metal concentration reduce plants morpology through accumulation with breaches to legal and regulatory requirements. Plants vie for room and food during the growing period as opposed to environmental protection and conservation in large industries and operations, especially in the mining industry, however, recent studies have identified aspects that distinguish between native acceptable population selection.

This section presents a literature review of plant species that can reduce excessive levels of heavy metal concentrations especially the metal with densities of more than five with can cause deformation and deaths to plant species. Regardless of the heavy metal concentration levels, there are plant species that are sighted growing in these sites with less deformation and are able to withstand and tolerate such toxicity and effects (Riddell-Black.,1993). Toxicity from heavy metals occur under various influential conditions as discussed earlier.

Heavily loaded sediments with high and accumulated concentration levels from the heavy metals in the sediments is a harmful condition with different influential factors. High concentration of metals in tailings are the causes of soil, surface and ground water contamination especially from large scale operations and mining and tailing (Kahale., 1993). The vegetation is site specifics and is influenced by one overriding factor called the metal concentration. It is observed that the habitats are distinct and the sequence and patterns of in hereditary shifts are responsible for settlement and establishment of metal contaminates as a sole record of natural selection in action. Toxic metals restrict growth and development in various environmental conditions (Dickinson & Lepp., 1997). Metals are micro and macro nutrients to plants. Excessive and large quantities are harmful to the plant species. Mine tailing sediments have high metal concentration levels compared to natural soils even though natural soils do have metal concentration levels. Site specific pollution by mine operation lead to environmental pollution from high toxic metal concentration levels. The curiosity levels with sighting plants growing and tolerating toxicated areas warrants for studies of recent trends of metal toxicity and tolerances in plants. Heavy metal concentration in the tailings storage facilities are accountable for physical and practical appearances and deficiencies sighted on plants species and appearances. Loss of leaves and reduced roots development and variations

in appearances as signs and symptoms of deficiencies are results of impacts by heavy concentrated metals. In hereditary genetic and biological tolerance for growth and development is still a mystery and is demonstrations of more scientific reasoning and beyond human jurisdiction give the interaction of concentration levels, growth media, soil chemistry and different weather and or climatic conditions Dickson et al. (1992). Their ability to be resistance, avoidance and even susceptible to this given conditions and tolerance is far beyond reasoning but can be scientifically proven. Factual tolerance requires evident based morphology, competition for nutrients and growth in terms of appearances and development in specific sites of metals with inherited forbearances.

Reallocation of roots to less concentrated heavy metal sites by facultative tolerance create conditions of regrowth and reestablishment from the struggles. I would recommend white clover and tephrosia for primary neutralisation of concentration as these species fix nitrogen as an essential element for plant growth and development into the soil for instigation of plant growth and can also contribute to colonisation with other plant species especially in mines with heavy metal concentration and disturbed and compacted soils (Borgegard & Rydin 1989).

The species can withstand adverse weather conditions so as different soil and metal composition interaction and even can colonize well in the habitat and growth medium. Comparisons of the soil concentration levels of the 7 species indicated chances of tolerance and growth with influence from the weather conditions. The species were also able to struggle and withstand adverse concentration levels in the heavy metals and yet climate is seen to be the driver on the strength of the concentration levels so as the plant morphology (Turner & Dickinson., 1993).

Morphology tolerances requires precise physical and mechanism with genomics (Dickson et al.,1991) however requires both induction and vanish in plants thus their ability to acclimatise fluctuating stress pollution which is considered imperative to morphology and susceptibility in plant species. Heavy metal contaminated soil adaptability and tolerance and survival requires characteristics of both avoidance and resistance mechanisms from physiological and biochemical abilities to withstand and response to different conditions and interactions which are inheritary over time Dickinson et al, 1992. The phenotype acclimatisation that determines plant species characteristics and features can be further studied of their inhereditary (Dickinson et al., 1992)

Plant species propagation from seedlings were used in this research so are the various researches done all over the world despite the adverse and influential conditions compared with matured plants and seedlings given their different levels of exposure, interactions and tolerance for survival and morphological changes. Seedlings are considered vulnerable to hostile environments and lead to unrealistic signs of the storage capacity of adult plant species (Riddell-Black., 1993). However, the reaction of seedlings or cuttings to heavy metal concentrations remains the usual means of extracting, tolerating and resisting such stress and resistance and comparing the ability of clones of different or same species to resist (Punshon et al.), 1995). .. However, it was unclear to what extent the observed resistance was genetically or environmentally induced. In further studies, Punshon and Dickinson (1997) showed that the gradual adaptation of trees to metal stress can increase their resistance to heavy metals of the species being pulled. Landberg and Greger (1994)

In general, most plants are harmed by high concentration of toxic metals, others are able to tolerate toxic habitat, the interaction of concentration levels and the growth medium whilst some species struggle as an effect on the given conditions with nutrients competition for morphological changes.

2.3. Heavy Metal Uptake by Trees Grown on Contaminated Substrates

It is known that heavy metals are absorbed and translocated by plants to different parts. The use of plants to decontaminate growth medium by heavy metal extraction reveals considerable means as a low – cost technique which has received much attention recently.

Phytoremediation application is emerging and is limited due to low biomass of hyperaccumulators, unavailability of the suitable plant species and long cultivation period requirements. Hence to maximise phytoextraction efficiency, it is vital to select species that are fast growing, can set sufficient biomasses and have the ability to absorb large amounts of heavy metal concentrations and be compatible with mechanised propagation techniques and local climate. This study assesses the potential for phytoremediation of heavy metal contaminated sediment invested tailing dam vicinity by selected plant species. In summary, its presence the research progress of phytoremediation by trees and suggest options in which this concept can be applied and improved over time.

Plants species absorb heavy metals and translocate to different parts. Bioavailability and successive accumulation of heavy metals on plant species very much depend on the sources of heavy metal concentration, contamination and habitat (Lepp & Eardley, 1978). Movement of heavy metal concentration in the soils and sediments depend on factors like pH, redox potential, cation exchange capacities, and presence of organic matter, earthen segments and biological interaction. The relationship between tissue metal accumulation and soil factors has been observed, and the overall accumulation and migration of heavy metal ions (especially chromium) depends on growth medium and sediment parameters, wood structure, ie cellulose and organic polymers. It extends to. As such, the studies done compared growth from absorption of heavy concentrated metal as the parameters of monitoring against the selected plant species and from the guard and control plots from the tailing sediments. It revealed that most of the species had greater concentration of lead and nickel in plant tissues whilst copper indicated less concentration thus less impact on the leaves and trunk. It indicated greater level of metal concentration in the leaves when grown in the tailings sediments infested with heavy metal concentration. Heavy metal concentration from sediments accumulate in fine roots more times than the fine roots of spruce and poplar accumulation respectively Brunner et al.,2008). Correspondingly Cd & Zn accumulate in various shrubs and puddle plants especially in the leaves and roots in terms of biomass (Unterbrunner et al., 2007)

Leaves infested with heavy metals were not only linked to sedimentation concentrated with heavy metals but were also from accumulating factors such as the concentration levels, interaction in the sediment, growth medium, chemistry and morphology along with influences from the predominant weather conditions from the selected heavy metals which tracked a contrary nature of requirement. Numerous studies and experiments have confirmed that the absorption of high concentrations of metals by different species of plant species depends on the age and characteristics of that species.

Parameters of heavy concentrated metals namely (Cd, Cu, Cr, Ni, Pb, Hg, and Zn) have been studied in proportion to lifespan and morphology in plants in my sites from which reveals several year-old plant species demonstrate efficient remediation with exhibition of greater resistance to trees and adaptability compared to a year-old species. The data analysis revealed presence and effects of heavy metals spike compared to the results given greater concentration levels in the sediment as the growth media. Studies show that year 1 tree samples showed a relatively high metal accumulation pattern within the tree species, but year 3 sample extraction

did not show a significant increase in concentration levels. Metal formation and accumulation in bulk coating. In contrast to willows and poplars, they show different growth and development rates over the course of the year (Lombini et al., 2003). It has also been reported that metal concentrations were high during early vegetative growth and developmental stages for relatively adequate nutrient absorption, as opposed to growth rate (Dinelli & Lombini, 1996). Active growth dilution concentration levels up to flowering stage, allowing assessment of seasonal differences and changes in metal concentration levels of contaminated dredged substrates cultured in *S. fragilis* L and *S. triandra* L. with akin sorts. Less proportion of total Cd was extracted by ammonium acetate in the six-year-old stand (6%) contrasted to one-year old stand (17%) which recommends the potential for removable of heavy metal concentration from the site which declined with tree age (Mertens et al., 2006). However, annual variation of Cd and Zn concentration levels in leaves of *Salix caprea* were less, signifying data obtained in different years can be related (Unterbrunner et al., 2007). In addition, seasonal differences of metal concentration levels in plants have been confirmed. Especially plant absorption for *S. armeria* is active in the root zones in the initial growth and development stages when the demand for nutrients are high as indicated also by increased macronutrients concentrations levels. Nevertheless, plant species morphology in tropical wet and dry seasons favour transpiration of metal concentrated translocation on plant tops as results or outcomes. In senescent stages metals have tendency to be concentrated in the plant species leaves similarly, it was revealed the tendency of increased copper content or concentration in willow leaf in period as a possible detoxification effect in contracting defoliation (Hasselgen, 1999). It was also reported that periodical variation of Cd and Zn concentration in leaves of *E. innovation* revealed inclination towards accumulation with leaf age from sprouting in Feb to leaf fall in Nov from the studies. As such the metal concentration (Cd, Cu, Cr, Ni, Pb, Hg, and Zn) steadily increased in the leaves and stems from the analysis of the trailed specimens in Oct compared to those collected in June which were explained in the leaf lifespan. Similarly, the concentration of aged leaves sampled in October was significantly higher than the concentration of mature leaves sampled in August for all metal parameters except Cu and Cr. Possible interpretations include air pollution, cuticle cracking, water loss, and / or long-term exposure to leaf rearrangement before aging. Metallic concentrations (Cd & Zn) in leaves, trees, plant stems and bark increased towards the end of the growing season, regardless of species. Heavy concentrated metal uptake can be strongly influenced by ectomycorrhizal fungi that can inoculate *Populus tremula* which may be reasonable strategy to improve revegetation and phytostabilization of heavy metal concentrated and contaminated sites. However, initial growth

stage of *P. tremula* may be limited by imbalance between fungal plant partner such as nutrient deficient and toxic environments (Langer et al., 2012).

Seven shrubs, secondary species and flowers growing around the mine Tailing Storage Facility have been selected and trailed out and analysed for their ability to be susceptible and grow with toleration to heavy metal concentration levels within the growth medium (mine waste tailing sediments) which indicated that leaves concentrated with Zn, Pb and Cd surpass values for leave growing in uncontaminated soils comparatively (Fernards and Henriques, 1989).

Copper, Pb and Zn had excessive attention distribution of extra than 50 time and 20 instances respectively which ended in increase retardation, decreased leaf size, sizeable necrotic and chlorotic recognizing with inside the plant species that have been grown within side the mining affected substrates. Stem and leaf sampling of seeds grown on mining substrates showed that metals were higher during early plant growth stages due to relative humidity and average nutrient absorption compared to growth and development. Concentration levels were diluted and almost naturalized in the initial growth stages then gradually depleted towards the flowering because moisture content and nutrients were competed so the minimal concentration levels were noted (Dinelli & Lombini, 1996). Tree senescence habitually indicate increased metal levels concentration due to loss of fluids. Other studies, similar to the two-year study of metal content in birch leaves, tracked different concentration levels of metal. This suggests that Cu and Ni concentration levels decreased during the first growing season, probably due to the diluting effect of dry weight leaves. (Ehlin, 1982). In contrast, at the end of the growing season, accumulation of Zn concentration levels was seen in all the leaves of the hanging plants (Ross, 1994). Metal concentrations in plant tissues have been found to occur prior to aging or due to seasonal differences in the availability of sediment concentrates. Steady increase in heavy metal concentration in leaves just before aging of willows contaminated with heavy metals and grown on contaminated substrates. The Cu concentration in willow leaves tends to increase periodically, which is interpreted as a possible detoxifying effect consistent with defoliation (Hasselgren, 1999). Therefore, where heavy metal concentrations were low, leaf, stem and bark concentrations and contamination of Cd, Cu and Zn were reduced during growth monitoring and slightly increased in plant species forests. In contrast plant species differ in their potential and ability to translocate heavy metals from the roots to the shoots where else in sludges grown in sludge amended growth medium revealed concentration of metals in the stems and leaves were in the order of incline less than the corresponding root levels (Lepp & Eardlry, 1978). Heavy metal concentration differs in different plant species thus the study of concentration

levels on Cu & Zn of the *Salix* species that affirms dissimilar patterns in the plant species so are the patterns of the two metal concentration levels (Nissen & Lepp, 1997). An overall trend of segregation of Cu & Zn concentration in shoot tissues and vessels relative to soil concentration with evidences though. The low Cu concentration was excluded from the shoot illustrating low mobility of Cu in the roots and relative to foliar uptake. In contrast, higher leaf and bark Zn concentrations indicate post-extraction element mobility, while lower wood concentrations indicate lower Zn retention in xylem tissue. Partitioning of metals between vessels and tissues alter in the growth medium as metals concentration and interaction levels increases. In contrast concentration levels of Zinc and Cd in the stems of *Salix viminalis* increased significantly in height as a consequence of increase in bark proportion principally (Sander & Ericson, 1998). The proportion of bark increases as the trunk tapers towards the tip of the shoot, which contains more nutrients than the tree. Ni mainly increases from the lowest to the highest sampling level, followed by Cu, Zn and Cd. During leaf aging, different elemental redistribution patterns occur, resulting in different levels of shoot concentration after the leaves have been dropped. The effect of nutrient availability on the metal element distribution pattern is also questionable.

Heavy metals are vital for wood and bark changes and development with supplementary vessels and tissues attachments added in every growing period. The tissues and vessels slowly enter decomposition cycles thus accumulate metal concentration levels and immobilise in inactive compartments for considerable periods and if the contaminated plant species are not utilised for other purposes shall revive return of heavy metals to the habitat as in effect such as combustion whilst woods with heavy metal concentration are usually less in the roots and barks from which the fraction may present a much more significant proportion of the total metal in trees (Dickson & Lepp, 1997).

2.4. Phytoremediation Using Trees

Phytoremediation is the process of using plants in partially or substantially repair pollutants selected from contaminated growth media, altered sludge, sediments, surface water, and wastewater. This innovation in the recent times has received attention as a cost effective and environmentally friendly alternative to treat and mitigate harmful and hazardous waste induced and accumulated sites (Aronsson and Perttu, 1994; Glimerveen, 1996; EPA, 1999 -2000). Phytoremediation is a biological repair process that uses plants partially or substantially repair

contaminants selected from contaminated growth media, modified sludge, sediments, surface water, and wastewater. Uses a variety of plant species and plant biological and physical properties to assist in site repair. It has also been termed and or worded in many ways such as green remediation, botano -remediation, agro-remediation and vegetative remediation. Phytoremediation has a range of processes with different processes occurring to opposing degrees with different conditions, media, contaminants and plants from which this literature review uses variety of the terms and wordings as convenient means of intellectualizing the processes that occur during phytoremediation. A number of options have been incorporated to degrade, remove (through accumulation or dissipation) and or immobilize of contaminants. Accomplishment of phytoremediation depends on the ability of plant species to absorb, extract and translocate heavy metals in line with their distinctive phenotypes and genotypes. The benefits of phytoremediation can emerge from soil stability, reduced contamination of soil and water from which the phytoextraction can be used to remediate soil with appropriate establishment and reestablishment of plant species.

The establishment and re-establishment of plant species in the mining operations sedimented areas and stockpiles that are heavily infested with heavy metals have higher chances of heavy metal concentration accumulation and settlement that contribute to struggles in plant growth and development. As such the root immobilisation is a norm in plant species in controlled and selective heavy metal extraction but are exposed to limitations in translocation drifting plant components. However, in least contaminated sites, morphology is induced by other influential factors such as concentration and metal interactions, deficiencies, climatic conditions, aerations, root penetration, water holding capacities and plants' abilities to adapt to prevailing and influential conditions and factors (Pulford & Mullins, 1991).

Properly aerated and tilted sites or well-prepared sites are conducive for plant species establishments which will prompt and instigate proper growth and development of plant. It is important to note that soils are natural seedbeds for millions of plant species dormant and readily available to grow once favourable conditions are created. In contrast the trials and for this study are done on sediments plots from the tailing dams infested with heavy metal concentration levels and mine spoils which are not homogenous or permeable in composition compared to other mine sites and their experiences in the struggle and competition for nutrients given the uneven spread and distribution of resources in the growth medium and study parameters (Merrington, 1995).

There is direct and indirect relationship in nutrient competition and mortality rates in the sedimented growth medium especially with more deaths and redundancies in growth and development from less availability of essential nutrients for morphology. There are however other key influential contributing factors that hinder growth and development in the mining sedimented growth medium and these are climatic conditions, chemistry and interactions by different heavy metal concentrations, growth medium, spacing and the plants characteristics in terms of its ability to adapt to different conditions and influences (Moffat, 1999).

Mine sites plant species selection and rehabilitation are difficult given the compacted and disturbed land availability presented with displaced topsoils and exposed subsoils which don't contain adequate nutrients and essential elements needed for morphological changes. Most of the soils and sediments are mine spoils and mostly are tracked run by heavy earth movers and plants thus the soils presented are compacted so soil aeration and pores are not readily available for root penetration for growth and development is the struggle and even to make it more worse is collection of sediments from the tailing dams for trials and research is a real challenge for favourable results compared to species trials and research from undisturbed and untapped native forested sites which have readily available essential elements and nutrients and even is a natural seed bed with dormant varieties of seeds awaiting conducive conditions to sprout. In the mine sites trials and research there have to be expectations for nutrient deficiencies, high acids, salinity and poor water holding capacities along with restricted rooting potentials as a result of less water and high bulk densities of the substrates. As mentioned earlier, this can be compared to plant species that grow in peripherally important lands in terms of fertility, texture and structure. However, there are many pioneering tree varieties, including willow cultivars, which show high survival and growth rates on a variety of substrates and climatic conditions. Most mine sites invest lots of monies in purchasing growth regulators and fertilizers to enhance plant growth for stabilisation, erosion control and heavy metal extraction on heavily compacted mine disturbed soils to be compliant with legal and regulatory requirements so as to revive nutrient deficiencies and to instil nutrient contents but plants don't last due to lack of aeration, root penetration and establishment in the given growth medium and conditions. However natural colonisation gradually creeps in overtime with weeds and algae as the first inhabitants on the disturbed areas in with description of cessation of root development at the interface of mine spoils and organic alteration (Johnson et al., 1977).

Plant species establishment with gradual colonisation by dispersible animals and windy conditions can assist with initial cover establishment. Algae, lichens and lycopodium are good initial colonisers along with weed and grass species. Their invasion and establishment and even development warrants for growth and development of secondary species and trees which become initial stabilizers and mitigates soil erosion from production of massive roots and biomasses can reduce soil erosion and absorb and dilutes heavy metal concentration levels (Johnson et al., 1992; Stomp et al, .1993). In addition plant species minimize the flow of water into the soils thus aiding dilution and cooling off of heat and interaction in the soil chemistry in the plant growth medium and in doing so distributes the concentration levels evenly in such a way that reduces harm to the plants with assistance from the sunlight through evapotranspiration of concentration level distribution once dissolved in water.

A method in phytoremediation called Phyto-stabilisation has physical and chemical effects. This method produces chemical compounds in the plants that immobilises contaminants and are not degraded with chemicals changes which makes it less available in vegetation and rehabilitation. There are elements than can be mobilized by vegetative cover (Chaney et al.1997). There are also options that deep rooting plant species could decrease highly toxic which is less soluble and bioavailable (James, 2001)

Apart from controlled research and trials, rehabilitation and revegetation in open disturbed areas especially from the mining settings, the chemistry in metals and their outcomes in terms of impacts and effects on the receiving plants are diverse with limited certainties in most cases in terms of metals availability to plant species. Plants have allowable limits of metal intake opposed to excessive intake which shall have negative impacts on the plants however plants may have mechanism to absorb excessive amount and manage them by redistribution insufficient components and even send back to the roots to be distributed to the other plants to uptake. There may be cases whereby excessive quantities absorption can be systematically neutralized with their system but too much in most cases can harm the plants especially in heavy metal concentrated and accumulated sites.

Plant accumulation, also known as plant extraction in phytoremediation, is the process by which the chemical compounds produced by the roots of a plant absorb contaminants along with other nutrients and water, thereby not destroying the mass of contaminants. But the land of plants. The method has advantages and features used primarily in containing metal and has the ability

to grow less fertile soils and sediments, has deep rooted system to hold weight, have fast growth rates and should have metal resistance traits (Punshon et al., 1996). Achieving deadlines and goals is paramount, regardless of metal concentration and location. Mining industries contribute to accumulation high contents and concentration levels with considerable sedimentation and environmental impacts especially river system dieback from sedimentation are critical concerns for the mine and environmental managements team. Reestablishment, revegetation and rehabilitation are crucial to address sedimentation to restore stability to erosion and impacts (Labrecque et al., 1995). On the other hand, if the species are susceptible to the conditions presented to them and are performing and growing vigorously and aiding with mitigation of accumulated heavy metal concentration and provision of stability to the impacted environment then there is no need for research nor phytoremediation as the balance and equilibrium in nature had taken its own course. There are always issues with acidic conditions formed and accumulated causing acid rock drainage from which non-acid forming material are used to cover the acidic conditions but when species grow and colonise, the acidic conditions are neutralized providing harmony with cover establishment on the surface.

Weed infestation, poor soil fertility, water storage and poor management practices also contribute to reduced growth and survival in plants desired for a specific purpose (Rees et al., 1998). With in-depth knowledge and science in plants can aid in improving their conditions of growth and development which will contribute to more survival and less mortality rates of the plant species (Dickson, 2000). It is true to say that all plant species invite, house and create an ecosystem for all forms of life to dwell from the well-nourished and fertile growth mediums for vigorous growth and survival. Death leaves and manure from all living things within the ecosystem and habitat interact to condition the soil type thus absorption of essential and needed metal levels for morphological changes.

2.5. Translocation and Compartmentalisation of Heavy Metals in Trees

Translocation of heavy concentration metals levels differs in all plant species and clones thus the research and trails to better understand the characteristics and behaviours as such, *Salix* and *Betula* species acknowledges transfer of zinc and cadmium to their leaves and twigs whilst *Fraxinus* and *Sorbus* omit them from their above ground selections (Rosselli et al., 2003). Differences in field grown and confined and controlled grown species were monitored for their translocation properties with differences pertaining to their growth medium and root interfaces.

The monitoring revealed that some plant species indicated poor translocation from the roots up to the shoots regardless of quantities and forms supplied whilst metals were voluntarily transferred from the roots in large quantities which were measured in leaves and shoots (Pulford et al., 2001). Regardless of typha being taxonomically diverse is a common swamp plant that predominantly grows in aqueous swamps and heavily water logged regions and in disturbed land puddles has the advantages of accumulating and partitioning heavily concentrated heavy metals with slim chances of survival in drier sites thus a selective species for planting and monitoring at times. Transpiration is an important “moving power” of heavy metals from the roots to the shoots. In this connection, Cd and Zn are gradually transported from the root to the leaf by transpiration during the growth phase, and the main elements are evenly distributed, so the transport of metal from the leaf blood vessels to the mesophyll cells is selected by the mechanism. Leaf tissue that may be restricted. There were similar results obtained from research and studies done. Transportation of ions are absorbed by roots and hence their migration to the above ground organs are executed through cell sap in the xylem. Immigration of heavy metals to superior parts of the plant species such as the leaves, leaves sheaths or shoot apices depend on several factors with most important being the heavy metal form and concentration whilst the other being the structure and ability of the shoot to form storage organs as well as the interactions between different elements.

The association of heavy metals in the environment and their relative chemical resemblance results in interactions between different metal concentration levels during plant uptake as well as transportation from the roots to above ground tissues and vessels. There was strong relationship among heavy metal concentration levels and bioaccumulation factors in the leaves. Branches and roots of the studied and monitored plant species had similar suggestions on transport mechanisms of the heavy metals. Translocation of heavy metals from the roots were higher in the leaves than stem and the combined treatment stimulated translocation of heavy metals from the roots to the leaves and stems however suppressed the translocation of other metals from the roots to the whole plant. Therefore, interaction effects were considered strongly synergistic with different metal interaction and results.

Distribution of various heavy metals were reliant of the type of metals and their behaviours. The main difference is the efficient compartmentalization of specific organ components. This is a comparison of various plant parts such as old leaves and bark of where the metal could not show such compartmentalization. Past studies revealed that zinc easily translocates to the

leaves whilst copper poorly translocates to the leaves. In a similar context, Cd stabilised in the roots of plants and greater amounts of Cd accumulated in the epidermis than cortex plus stele. Both Cd and Zn were found to accumulate in the petioles and veins of leaves and barks of twigs of the plant species.

Zinc was the most profuse pollutant in both soil and vegetation along with cadmium preferentially accumulated in older foliage of the trailed species in growth media mixed with contamination where else excess copper and lead were not translocated. Excess zinc was unevenly accumulated in leaves tissues having a tendency to saturate the veins and vessels were more frequently stored in cell symplast than apoplast. Metabolic and subcellular storage compartments incur metal accumulation thus stress and reactions from interactions. Zinc complexation by phytate contributed to metal detoxification and accumulation in foliage but couldn't eradicate and prevent toxicity reactions therein.

2.6. The Phytoremediation Potential of willow (*Salix spp.*)

This research has itemised various phytoremediation technologies, methods and plant species available to mitigate the contamination levels induced by heavy metals. With deep root systems and biomass yields, plant species have high economic and environmental value, are more cost effective than traditional restoration methods such as soil drilling, pumping and treatment systems, and provide environmentally friendly technology. Although phytoremediation appears to be an effective method for wide range of heavy concentrated metals, the biological means behind effective plant species use of contaminant mitigation are largely unknown. Hence there are influential factors that require study in the areas of interactions between growth media and various metal concentration levels and their interactional capabilities, the roots and interactions and nutrient competition along with microbes and biotechnologies for phytoremediation.

There have been studies done earlier on *Salix* or poplar plant species because of their advantage of good biomass establishments, fast growths and short rotations. It revealed that *Salix* cultivation offers effective options for addressing cadmium accumulation especially in the humus layers and topsoils with high cadmium contents from anthropogenic inflows and the subsoils contained little cadmium naturally.

Genus *Salix* is an adherent of Salicaceae plant family. There are 200 registered hybrids out of 400 species of willow that have been discovered (Newsholme, 1992). Most of the genus of *Salix* predominantly grow in the lowlands and wetland habitats have assortment hybrid progenies (Sommerville, 1992). Many species and hybrids of *Salix* suggests wide genetic variability within the genus. *Salix* also have creeping forms such as *Salix repens* and willow bushes such as *Salix cinerea*. There are few species of *Salix* that have single trunked trees that can grow over to 20m in height such as *Salix alba*.

Shoots and roots can still grow vigorously from a copied stool from fallen trunks and branches (Sommerville, 1992). There are many species that are known to colonize edaphically in hostile and extreme soils and the genus namely are; *S.caprea*, *S.cinerea* and the hybrid *S.viminalis* (Dickson et al., Dickson et al., 1994) There are detailed reputation of willow that colonise heavy metal contaminated and dried silts removed from a port that depicted attention to suitability of selected clones for planting in polluted areas (Mang, 1992). The soil consolidated provide enmeshment of spreading roots is an aspect that can be exploited in revegetation and reclamation of land. The demand and need for perennial root system of willow in water reduces the risk of contaminants leaching and seeping and most plant species are unable to tolerate dry and drought periods (Sander & Ericson, 1998).

The distinctive and advantageous characteristics of willow makes it a vital and suitable tree in phytoremediation because it can be regularly harvested by coppicing yields as much as 10 – 15 dry tonnes per hectare per year (Riddell – Black, 1993). *S. viminalis* is one of the most commonly used plant species, and bushy willow species with upright stems, rapid growth, and excellent rooting ability are better suited for biomass bushes. (Ahman & Larsson, 1994). With respect to high biomass productivity, *Salix* tree species advantageously have an effective nutrient uptake capacity, high evapotranspiration rate and is a distinct clone that has a specific capacity for taking up heavy metals.

The likely end product uses of *Salix* biomass include fuel for direct burning as wood chips, raw materials for production of papers, clipboards and charcoals, a source of viscose for the fabrics production, weaving of basket and making of blocks, ethanol and forage enhancement of ruminant livestock (McElroy & Dawson, 1996). Wood fuel use could possibly allow heavy metal recovery through scrubbing of smoke gases and proper handling of ashes (Perttu & Kowalik, 1997; Dahl, 2000). There are two possible strategies that have been proposed for the

use of willow for phytoremediation (Punston et al., 1995). First, willows, which survive in contaminated soils with low metal uptake into air tissues, are best used to avoid the spread of heavy metals into the wider environment or the attribution of metals to the food chain. It is suitable. When soil restoration is achieved by plant extraction and tree harvesting, it is desirable to accumulate relatively high levels of metal (Guo et al., 2012). Several tactics have been invented to study and study the uptake of willow clones, taking into account unpaved roads, greenhouse experiments, and hydroponic cultivation scheme. Landberg and Greger (1994) tested various clones for Cd and Zn accumulation and tolerance in solutions culture (Fernandez et al., 2008) revealed that Cd accumulation in above ground tissues showed differences among clones and the use of selected clones of woody fleabane and mycorrhization of white birch enhance efficiency from contaminated soils in phytoremediation work.

Some clones were tolerant to both metals and others were to tolerant to just one clone which could have relatively high or low net uptake of metals with the net transport to the shoots ranging from 1% - 72% of the total metal uptake (Mleczek et al., 2010) and later revealed substantial variances in accumulation efficiency among *Salix* clones. The difference between the highest and the lowest heavy metal content in extreme clones were 84% for Cd, 90% for Cu, 167% for Hg, 190% for Pb and 36% for Zn.

The Cd uptake capacity of 70 *Salix* genotypes can differ 43-fold between the highest and lowest range clones (Greger, 1999). Better assortment had about 5 times higher capacity than the hyperaccumulators *T. caerulescens* and *Alyssum murale* for high biomass production and transport of Cd to the chute. *Salix viminalis* showed the highest metal storage capacity in various plant tests and achieved a Cd migration factor of 3.4 in field tests on contaminated soil. *Salix viminalis* showed the highest metal storage capacity in various plant tests and achieved a Cd transfer coefficient of 3.4 in lanes of contaminated soil.. However, the calculated 77 years to decontaminate the soil used in the study to acceptable Cd concentration levels were not practicable highlighting the limitations of yields and or metal uptake rates of phytoextraction as a remediation implement (Felix, 1997).

Metal concentration levels in stem calculation are to be achieved to reduce metal concentration in a polluted soil to target concentration over 30 years which is the expected production life of willow grown on a short rotation (Riddell - Black, 1993). It was indicated that decontamination of highly contaminated land could not be achieved in short term due to very high concentration

of metals requirements in the stems. Remediation of less contaminated land could be attained in a reasonable time scale even with low metal uptake due to frequency of harvest. Salix's success as a plant-extracted plant depends on its biomass production, the ability and potential of metal storage, and the location of metal storage within the plant.. Uptake of heavy metals by four varieties of Salix used in woodchip production for energy were measured. The trees were grown for three years on growth medium that had received sludge for over 50 years. The main benefit for Salix growth on this metal contaminated site was reported to be stable to take up metal but the harvested biomass was not sufficient for accurate phyto-extraction. However, growth of Salix maybe useful if depletion of the bioavailable metal in soils occur. There are inspiring indications of this happening from other sites. About 30% of the bioavailable Cd was removed by Salix in a 90day trail pot and concentration of exchangeable Cd in 8 soils taken from Salix stands and from nearby unplanted reference soils were 30% – 40% lower in the planted growth media. Total Cd concentration were not significantly reduced but the exchangeable Cd pool was reduced. From the depth of 65cm of the soil profile absorption takes place. However, effects of the growth of the five tree species including willow over the six years on Cd soil concentration indicated high Cd uptake was not related to a corresponding depletion on the soluble Cd pool. This pool increased with lower pH (Alriksson et al., 1999). (Alriksson et al., 1999)

Heavy metal concentrations in the bark and wood of 20 willow species were measured (Pulford et al., 2002). Overall, the concentration of the 3-year-old tree showed certain clones that could absorb significant amounts of metal. Cd concentration in stem in this study were up to an order or magnitude greater than soil concentrations. There was also indication of various Salix clones compartmentalised Cd in woody tissues much more marked than others representing a beneficial trait for long term removal of contaminants from the soils (Pulford et al., 2002). Uptake by willow exceeds air deposition and fertilizer input in the range of 2-5% of the Cd made available to the soil by plants from the studies studied, and the concentration of Cd in a rotation cycle of about 20-25 years. Suggested that was below the natural limit (Ostman, 1994). Commercially grown Salix reports an annual accumulation of 20.30 g Cd per hectare (Goransson & Philippot, 1994)

Number of studies have supported this observation that Cd uptake by willow from moderately contaminated growth media maybe sufficient to allow clean up within few years. Also, one, hyperaccumulator of Cd, *T. caerulescens* (Brooks, 1998) is known and there is considerable

potential to exploit this ability to take up large amounts of Cd. Cd is very toxic and is a well-known contaminant in habitats. Hence the use of willow to remove Cd from moderately contaminated soils maybe the most immediate practical application of phytoremediation.

The overall trend of omission of Cu and accumulation of Zn in shoot tissue of eight *Salix* species identified by Nissen and Lepp (1997) indicated low potential for the depletion of soil Cu through repeated harvests, however Zn has some potential. Experimental research was done of salix clones in heavy metal contaminated dirt in partitions of metals and plants Dickinson et al, 1994. Mining disturbed dirt indicate high concentration of Zn from translocation from roots to the shoots respectively during harvest viable. Zn concentration levels alter with changes in seasons thus winter indicates good harvesting time in line with chuppon and pruning practices to enhance regeneration and growth McGregor et al, 1996.

However, it is suggested that dilution of Zn concentration level shall take a long time in several eras as estimated on a time scale to required limited. Regarding the use of metals in sludge, we evaluated the in vivo accumulation of various metals by *Salix discolor* and *S. viminalis*. About 50% to 80% of the total amount of bioaccumulated metal was found in the biomass of root and stem branches. This represents metal immobilization compared to the metal accumulated in the leaves returned to the soil at the end of each growing phase (Labrecque et al., 1994). The metal transfer coefficients of Cd and Zn were higher than those of Ni, Cu, and Pb. Increasing metal application to trees does not necessarily increase the metal concentration of lead tissue, but since Cd and Zn depend on soil concentration, there is less concentration of Cu, Ni and Pb in trees. Plants and metals show high solubility in these soil solutions and show species preference for them (Labrecque et al., 1995). The resistance and accumulation levels of Cd, Cu and Zn in the stems of different willow clones grown in metal-contaminated and uncontaminated sites were measured. There was no difference in willow resistance to metal or the concentration of selected items between the contaminated area and the control area. However, the growth of clones from contaminated areas was generally stimulated with low metal concentrations. The difference between accumulation and resistance to heavy metals was greater within species than between species. Heavy metals were larger within the species than between the species. Clones from the contaminated area had higher metal accumulation in their roots and a lower translocation of metals to the shoots probably to mechanism to protect the shoots (Landberg & Greger, 1996). There was also another investigation into the resistance of *Salix* to Zn, Cd and Ni in hydroponic experiments which revealed considerable variation between and within clones

(Punshon and Dickson, 1999). Resistance was not species-specific, but clone- or hybrid-specific. Significant intraclonal mutations were demonstrated by the viability of cleavage of some of the most sensitive clones in the high metal regimen. And to put this into context, large variation on *Salix* growth in uncontaminated soils was acknowledged. The phytoremediation screening program was difficult due to difficult variation process but maybe less essential in allowing provision of a remediation technique for a site through selective planting. However, it was concluded that fine tree roots adapt well to conditions with heavy metal contamination but their phytostabilizatoin capabilities seen to be very low. This variation caused difficulties in phytoremediation screening programs but may be essential in allowing provision of a remediation technique for a site through selective planting. However, fine roots adapt to heavy metal and contamination infested regions have low chances of stability by plants (Brunner et al. 2008).

CHAPTER 3: MATERIALS AND METHODS

Phytoremediation is the use of plants to clean up contaminated soils, sediments and water by heavy metals at a relatively low cost.

In this study, seven species of plants currently used by the remediation team for the rehabilitation program on the exposed areas and contaminated sites within the mine area, including the tailing dam were used. These species were selected based on their adaptive modes of being found predominantly growing in high rainfall areas, and altitude ranging from mid to upper montane, and also possessing shallow rooting systems. However, their use for phytoremediation in heavily contaminated areas such as the tailing waste is a challenge which this study was aimed at investigating, for plants that have phytoremedial characteristics and possession of the following attributes:

1. Have exceptionally high metal- accumulating capacity or are hyper accumulators.
2. Having roots possessing unique and selective capability to absorb.
3. Having entire structures that can translocate, bio-accumulate, and degrade the heavy metals
4. Having large above ground biomass and also possess extensive shallow rooting systems.
5. Having the ability to take up both essential and non-essential heavy metals.

3.1. Materials

The materials used in the research are in two categories, the field-based materials and requirements and the lab materials and requirements.

The Lab based materials used were latex white gloves, sample trays, double deionized water, ultra – pure acids used for the sediment digestions were nitric acids (HNO₃-), Hydrofluoric acid, hydrochloric acid(HCl), volumetric flasks, lab aprons and the inductively coupled plasma – optical emission spectrometry(ICP-OES), micro wave assisted digestion unit, questron microprep Q20 microwave digested system, 4 x digestion vessels, sediment core trays, freezer and pestle mortar for sieving, liners for samples and rupture disks were used.

In the field, 5 x labour, shade cloths, timbers, nails, vehicle, spades, digging fork, pegs and permo tags, biros, note books, safety boots and work coveralls, hand gloves, clear safety glasses were used as illustrated in the material requirements diagram below.

The metals selection for this research were based on plant species ability and success in absorbing contaminants, one of the categories of phytoremediation called phyto extraction was able to remove heavy metals from soils using its ability to uptake metals which are essential for plant growth along with metals with unknown biological functions and characteristics, that the heavy metals are elements with metallic properties and atomic numbers of >20 and the most common metals are Cd, Cr, Cu, Hg, Pb, and zinc and all are natural compounds in soil. Some metals are considered micronutrients necessary for plant growth whilst others have unknown biological functions. Metal pollution have harmful effects on biological systems and do not undergo biodegradation. Heavy metals can be differentiated from other pollutants as they not be biodegraded but can accumulate in living organisms causing harm and are also known to have effect on plant growth, ground cover and have negative impacts on soil microflora. It is also well known that heavy metals cannot be chemically degraded and need to be physically removed or be transformed into non-toxic compounds thus the selection of the several heavy metals concentrations for this research as illustrated in the figure below.

The data presented were obtained from seeds, wildings, and cuttings of 7 species of plants used in the rehabilitation program in the disturbed areas of the tailing storage facility vicinity. The plants are randomly selected for monitoring and analysis, and are grass plants, shrubs, secondary species, and legume plants.

The seeds collected were sun-dried and germinated in nursery sheds, and were transplanted into the tailing sediment trail plot beds. However, some seeds were collected from the surrounding bushes and exposed area and sowed directly into the trial plots.

The beds prepared were plot sizes of 1m x 10m with a depth of 30 cm, and were established near the tailing storage facility vicinity.

Figure 3. 1. The images below depict the species used in the trials

3.2. Methods

3.2.1. Study Site

The study was conducted on the tailing waste concession of the Ok Tedi Mining Ltd. Gold, Copper, and Silver mine located in the North Fly District, Western Province, Papua New Guinea (-5016'30.0"S , 141°13'35.0" E), 457 m above sea level. This area is the largest Cu reserve in the country. Residues from the extraction of Cu and other residual wastes are stored

in tailing ponds which contain extremely high concentrations of Nickel, Copper, Zinc, Mercury, Cadmium, Chromium and Lead ($>10,000 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$). The mine is still in operation and generates more sediment loads. A reference site in the Dump site, 480 m above sea level from Daru ($-5016'30.0''\text{S}$, $141^{\circ}13' 35.0'' \text{ E}$), was also selected for a field trial experiment. The average minimum temperature and total rainfall at Tabubil is 20°C and $8,000 \text{ mm}$, respectively, and is 94 km away from Kiunga, with a Tropical Rainforest usually found $100 - 150^{\circ}$ latitude of the equator.

Figure 3.2. Below is an image depicting the exact location of trials and preparation.

3.2.2. Location of Research

The research was done in the Tailing Pond Site of the Mill Waste Tailing Dump that stores all the waste residuals discharged as waste from the milling process of the mined ore at 480 m above sea level from Daru ($-5016'30.0''\text{S}$, $141^{\circ}13' 35.0'' \text{ E}$). Plots were developed near the tailing storage facility approximately 30 m above the storage facility on a higher flat ground or surface area.

Figure 3.3. Shows the Study location

3.2.3. Plots Construction

The Land area for trials was prepared 30 m above the Tailing Storage Facility. There were 10 x plots constructed and prepared for pouring of tailings sediments. The parameter plots were constructed with timber reinforced walls in each plot to contain all the sediments and turbulences in the area due to blasting. The bed size of each of the plot is 10 m x 1 m size plots and sediment poured to the brim of the beds aligned with the timber top surface to about 30 cm thickness in each plot. The plots were left to allow excess water to seep for several days and dry up before actual planting distances were marked on the plots for commencement of planting. All the plots were demarcated with wooden posts and covered or sheltered with shade cloths (50% shade green sheaths) over each plot as depicted in the images below.

The actual preparation and constructions were systematic done in a step by step process to actual planting then onto sample analysis and interpretation. The process began with as mentioned, the site preparation and construction of plots with off cut timber pieces, once the beds were completed, samples obtained from the locations 1 – 11 were poured in numerical

order of samples in each and once all the beds were properly filled to the brim, each plot were paired with trailed species and controls and other without trialled species.

The seedlings were planted; monitored and raw data obtained were recorded and harvested and weighed then dried. The dried specimens were prepared and analysed for metal concentrations and biomass sets. The site preparation images below indicate actual works.

Figure 3.4. Below are images of the plots preparation and trail plots planting for monitoring.

3.2.4. Collection of Plant Species

The 7 plant species trailed were sourced from two sources; one from the established site nursery used for rehabilitation, and the others were collected from the surrounding or wild to compare their ability to withstand the heavily concentrated heavy metal sediments. The species are namely: White clover – *Trifolium repens*, which is a leguminous plant; Tephrosia – *Tephrosia vogelii*, a shrub, which is also a leguminous plant; Kikuyu – *Pennisetum clandestinum*, a creeping grass; Lupin – *Lupinus maxicans*, a flower; Homantus – *Homalantus afakiensis*, a secondary tree species; Typha – *Typha latifolia*, a swamp area grass specie; and Trema – *Trema orientalis*, a legume and a secondary plant species used in the research trail plots infested with heavy metal concentrated sediments from the tailing storage dump.

Lupin, Typha and Kikuyu were obtained from the surrounding, as they were already growing there in the wild, while the other 4 species out of the 7 were raised in the rehabilitation nurseries; thus, were used for the research trials.

The different species of plants are shown below:

Figure 3.5. Illustrates the species trailed out in this research

3.2.5. Planting

The species were collected and transplanted from the nursery to the sediment plots, and were recorded before planting. The plant species were planted with a segment of each plot with each species, and spaced. About 2 metre segments of the plot were given to each plant species in

different spacing ranging from 1 m x 1 m to 4 m x 4 m. The 3 remaining plots of the 10 plots were planted with randomly picked or selected plant species of the 7 species as a mixture to observe and monitor performance, and also observe its colonizing potential and adaptability chances. Once the plantings were completed, all the plants were deemed for monitoring and observation.

In there were 2135 plants used in the trial of which 305 seedlings were from each of the 7 species. All trial species at 1m x1m spacing required 25 plants, 2m x 2m required 67 plants, and 3m x 3m required 113 and at 4m x 4m required 100 plants. To obtain the plant population a formula was used and that is Plant population = Total Area (m²) divided by (row spacing x plant spacing) which gave all the number of plant population required in each bed. In this case a sample would look like from the table below (100 plants = Area (4m x4m) change to centimetres to be consistent thus 160000cm ÷ (row spacing x inter plant spacing) which is 40cm x 40cm thus 160000 ÷1600 = 100 plants required in the 4m x 4m spacing. The total number of plants used in the different plot sizes and inter plant spacing is illustrated in the table below.

Table 3.1. Indicates the Plant Species and their spacing.

Plant Species Planted at Different Spacing									
#	Plant type	Plot Sizes (m) & Inter Plant Spacing (cm)				Total Planted Population			
		1m x1m	2m x2m	3m x3m	4m x4m	1m x1m	2m x2m	3m x3m	4m x4m
1	Trema	20cm x20cm	20cm x 30cm	20cm x 40cm	40cm x 40cm	25	67	113	100
2	Kikuyu	20cm x20cm	20cm x 30cm	20cm x 40cm	40cm x 40cm	25	67	113	100
3	White Clover	20cm x20cm	20cm x 30cm	20cm x 40cm	40cm x 40cm	25	67	113	100
4	Tephrosia	20cm x20cm	20cm x 30cm	20cm x 40cm	40cm x 40cm	25	67	113	100
5	Homalantus	20cm x20cm	20cm x 30cm	20cm x 40cm	40cm x 40cm	25	67	113	100
6	Typha	20cm x20cm	20cm x 30cm	20cm x 40cm	40cm x 40cm	25	67	113	100
7	Lupin	20cm x20cm	20cm x 30cm	20cm x 40cm	40cm x 40cm	25	67	113	100
	Total	305 plants from each species were used at different spacing				175	469	791	700

3.2.6. Sediment Sampling

3.2.6.1 Hydrological Data

The hydrological cycle in PNG is determined by the topography and climatic conditions. The two major air streams discussed earlier provide different sources of moisture at different times during a year. The south-easterly trade winds from May to August are accompanied by noticeable windward and leeward rainfall effects brought about topographic effects. From December to April, during the southern summer, the ITCZ is over PNG and heavy rainfalls are caused by winds coming from both the north and south to most of PNG.

Tabubil Western Province of Papua new is situated in the West of Papua New Guinea and is considered the wettest locations in the country with an average annual rainfall ranging from 3000 - 8000mm/year. It has a tropical rainforest climate

In a day a rainfall can 1.5mm – 50mm as an estimate. The mean rainfall ranges from 10 – 20mm/month and about a 100 – 150mm/year. The maximum ranges from 40mm – 100mm per month and 500 – 1000/year. There are always more wet days in a month than dry days ranging from 16 – 28 days respectively in the area.

3.2.6.2 Preparation for Sediment Sampling

Sampling gear such as latex hand gloves, spades, buckets, note books and pencils and clocks were prepared prior to sampling. Appropriate Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) such as rain coats, gumboots, cover rolls, dusk masks, and tape measures were also prepared prior to sampling. Preparation for sampling also included designing the areas to be sampled, and sampling method to be utilized in the tailing waste area.

At sampling preparation, the sediment samples were fetched from 11 different sites ranging from location 1 – location 11 from late 2017 from the tailing storage facility. The eleven samples were taken from the aqueous sections in the puddle bed and bottom of the periphery sections. The sample collections pattern is depicted in Figure 3.1. W - Shaped random sampling pattern.

In the preparation stage of sampling; the following steps were involved from the sample preparation to collection; a sampling procedure was developed in line with mining safety and

sampling safety prior to sampling inside the tailing dam. A thing to do list was developed as well in line with the safe sampling procedure and also developed a sampling pattern in the dam.

The following sampling gear were on sources and they included; a boat to do sampling an sampling bags and seals, 20kg zinc drums, latex gloves, rubber gloves, safety glasses and waiders, coveralls and life jackets, spades, labour, grab sampler, weighing scale and dust masks

The samples for analysis were taken beneath the water at a depth of 1 meter in accordance with the safe procedure; the samples were pulled out of the dam, weight whilst in the aqueous form and covered in zinc drum from the 11 locations and were taken to the lab for analysis preparation and analysis

The sediment samples were sealed and kept vertical in order to prevent mixing during transportation to the laboratory. Before slicing, all samples were preserved in 2 ± 0.2 cm sections in a freezer at 4°C. Slice samples were dried at 80–110 °C and then grounded with a pestle and mortar and sieved ($< 63 \mu\text{m}$).

The $< 63 \mu\text{m}$ fraction was used for analyses due to strong association of metals with fine-grained sediments (Horowitz and Elrick, 1987; Moore *et al.*, 1989; Goh and Chou, 1997; Tam and Wong, 2000; Che *et al.*, 2003). Many previous studies on sediment evaluation of metals from sediments used this size fraction (Usero *et al.*, 1998; Martin *et al.*, 1998; Morillo *et al.*, 2004; Guevara *et al.*, 2004; Yuan *et al.*, 2004). The sediment data in this study were analysed and interpreted in the results and discussion sections of this research.

3.2.6.3 Method of Sampling

Sampling method used was a random W-shaped pattern as a representation of the whole 400 m² marked area (illustrated in Figure 3.1, below). A 20 m x 20 m area was marked in the sediment concentrated area of the Tailing Storage Section. The sampling points were numbered from 1 to 11 for easy specimen arrangement, and handling and storage for analysis.

Figure 3.6. W-shaped random sampling.

3.2.6.4 Sediment Sample Collection.

The two year control period with periodic samplings intervals completed in October 2019 with samples taken from May, July, September and October in a weekly sequence from Week 1 of May, Week 2 of July, Week 3 of September, and Week 4 of October, respectively. The stations were chosen to arbitrarily store sediment settlement and were in aqueous form for sampling. The sediment samples were collected from 10 – 20 cm depth from the middle of the assigned sampling point from the tailing dump bank (congested with solid sediments deposited areas), but since was still shallow, it was possible to take the samples from the other marked and pegged areas in the Storage Facility. The sediment samples were collected into impenetrable polyethene sacks with the help of the bed material sampler. All the collected samples were transported to the lab and air dried for 72 hours, grounded in a total mortar, sieved to less than 63 μm sediment fraction and homogenized before each weighing. Sampling equipment were washed with double-distilled water and dried before use.

3.2.6.4 Preparation of Sediment Samples.

The core samples were sealed and kept vertically in order to prevent mixing during transportation to the laboratory. Before slicing, all samples were preserved in 2 ± 0.2 cm sections in a freezer at 4°C. Slice samples were dried at 80–110 °C and then grounded with a pestle and mortar and sieved (< 63 μm).

The < 63 μm fraction was used for analyses due to strong association of metals with fine-grained sediments (Horowitz and Elrick, 1987; Moore *et al.*, 1989; Goh and Chou, 1997; Tam and Wong, 2000; Che *et al.*, 2003). Many previous studies on sediment evaluation of metals from sediments used this size fraction (Usero *et al.*, 1998; Martin *et al.*, 1998; Morillo *et al.*, 2004; Guevara *et al.*, 2004; Yuan *et al.*, 2004). The sediment data in this study are reported on a dry weight basis.

3.3 Reagents, Equipment, and Quantitative Analyses of Sediments

Double deionised water (18 M Ω /cm) supplied by an ELGA water purifier was used. Ultra-pure acids were used for sediment digestion. Sediment extractions were conducted using a microwave-assisted digestion unit. The Questron MicroPrep Q20 Microwave Digestion System with four digestion vessels was used for microwave assisted acid digestion procedures. Samples were placed in liners (TFM Teflon, softening point 250°C) which are mounted in ultem caps. The vessels support an operating pressure of 350 psi and a maximum temperature of 260°C and they are resistant to HF. Rupture disks have been positioned withinside the Over Pressure Valve Stems withinside the vessels to emerge as a stress manage tool withinside the digester. The machine lets in the digestion of 4 samples on the identical time. Three different digestion programmes labelled as P1, P2 and P3 were tested with the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Standard Reference Materials (SRMs) to optimize a procedure for the tailings sediment. 0.1 g of sample was used for each digestion. Combinations of nitric acid (65 % HNO₃- used for easily oxidizable material), hydrofluoric acid (40 % HF- used for extraction of inorganic matrices), and hydrochloric acid (37 % HCl) were added to each of the digestion vessels. For microwave-assisted digestion procedures, the total extraction time was set at 26 min. The maximum strength carried out for all strategies become six hundred watts, held for 1 min in P1 and P2, and a couple of min for P3. Zero point eight ml of HCl become brought to the acid combination for P2 and P3. The details of the heating programmes used are given in Table 2. The digestate obtained were then filtered through a 0.45 μm membrane filter, diluted to 20 ml for storage and further analyses. For accurate results, all the extraction procedures were done in triplicate.

Table 3.2: Microwave-assisted Acid Digestion Programmes for Extraction Optimization.

Programme	Sample weight (g)	Reactives and Consumptions	Prog. step	Power (W)	Time (min)
P1 (26 min)	0.1	65% HNO ₃ (3ml) 40% HF (1ml)	1	200	7
			2	400	8
			3	600	1
			4	0	10
P2 (26 min)	0.1	65% HNO ₃ (3ml) 40% HF (1ml) 37% HCl (0.8 ml) (Total reactives volume: 4.8 ml)	1	200	7
			2	400	8
			3	600	1
			4	0	10
P3 (26 min)	0,1	65% HNO ₃ (3ml) 40% HF (1ml) 37% HCl (0.8 ml) (Total reactives volume: 4.8 ml)	1	200	7
			2	400	6
			3	600	2
			4	0	10

Digests were then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min to obtain a clear supernatant, and the supernatant transferred into a clean 100 mL volumetric flask. The residue was washed with deionized water and quantitatively added to the supernatant in the 100 mL volumetric flask, and finally diluted to the mark. Finally, multi elemental analyses using Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES), that uses the emission lines to identify and quantify the elements present, was used for quantitative analyses. Samples were introduced into the plasma and underwent processes such as desolvation, ionisation, and excitation so the constituent elements were identified by their characteristic emission lines and quantified by the intensity of the same lines. The instrument parameters for metal analysis were recommended by Grasshoff *et al.* (1999). From the SRM study it was concluded to use procedure P3 for the tailing sediments since recoveries over 95 % were obtained on the NIST SRM samples.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Potential of phytoremediation technique for the treatment of heavy metal-contaminated sites

This section discusses the potential of phytoremediation technique for the treatment of heavy metal-contaminated sites, to provide a brief overview about heavy metals uptake mechanisms by plants, to give some description about the performance of several types of plants in their uptake of heavy metals, and to describe the fate of heavy metals, especially arsenic (As), lead (Pb), mercury (Hg), Cadmium (Cd), Copper (Cu), Zinc (Zn), Tin (Sn) Lead (Pb), and Chromium(Cr), in plant tissue.

It had been predetermined that the trials of the seven plant species and heavy-metal-concentrated sediment trails and composition analysis from the tailing storage facility (TSF) and their interaction and combination was to help us conclude that hyper-accumulating plants must have a high quantity of heavy metal contained in their different plant structures by biomass. Also, to identify and recognise the species that can detoxify the soil of the toxic heavy metals by absorbing, stabilizing and accumulating the heavy metals in its different plant structures; roots, stem and leaves; and in doing so identify the species that are suitable for the phytoremediation and rehabilitation process of the mined site.

The Tables and Figures presented in this chapter are some of the recorded outcomes from the study.

Table 4.1: Plant Species Trailed

No	Common Name	Scientific Name	Remarks	Images
1	White Clover	<i>Trifolium repen</i>	Lugume	
2	Lupin	<i>Lupinus maxicans</i>	Flower	
3	Trema	<i>Trema orientalis</i>	Secondary plant	
4	Homalantus	<i>Homalantus populifolius</i>	Secondary Plant	
5	Tephrosia	<i>Tephrosia vogelii</i>	Legume/shrub	
6	Kikuyu	<i>Pennisetum clandestinum</i>	Grass/Creeper	
7	Typha	<i>Typha latifolia</i>	Swamp Grass	

Table 4.1 and 4.2 and Figure 4.1, indicate individual heavy metals and their average concentrations in mg/kg and standard deviations. The Standard deviation of metals indicated high level of lead, followed by zinc and nickel, and the rest with a trend that indicated less level in the sediment over the period of observation. The trend of growth and development of plants showed stunted and mortality rates related to high accumulation of heavy metals in the plant tissues especially in the leaves and stems. The influential factor of concern on the fluctuations in the concentration levels are the weather interaction with plant growth, and uptake of heavy metals and changes in soil chemistry from different conditions and changes.

Table 4.2: Sampled Locations before Field Planting

Year	Month	Date	Site	Pb mg/kg	Cu mg/kg	Zinc mg/kg	Cr mg/kg	Ni mg/kg	Cd mg/kg	Hg mg/kg
2019	Apr	2.04	A	0.29	1.8	2.6	0.010	0.100	0.010	1.90
2019	Apr	2.04	B	6.00	0.10	7.6	0.142	0.100	0.010	0.10
2019	Apr	2.04	C	7.40	0.50	7.6	0.202	0.700	0.700	0.10
2019	Apr	2.04	D	16.30	0.60	6.6	0.234	0.600	0.100	0.30
2019	Apr	2.04	E	18.00	0.70	5.8	0.314	0.500	0.200	0.20
2019	Apr	2.04	F	5.90	0.20	5.5	0.037	0.100	0.030	0.20
2019	Apr	2.04	F	15.20	1.00	8.1	0.230	0.300	0.030	0.10
2019	Apr	2.04	G	3.70	0.20	7.0	0.202	0.700	0.070	0.28
2019	Apr	2.04	H	2.20	1.50	6.3	0.224	0.300	0.030	0.01
2019	Apr	2.04	I	17.00	1.30	21.4	0.207	1.60	0.080	0.01
2019	Apr	2.04	J	11.80	0.40	0.6	0.027	0.015	0.120	0.01
Average				9.44	0.76	7.2	0.166	0.460	0.130	0.29
Standard Deviation				6.432	0.572	5.230	0.100	0.460	0.200	0.54

4.2. Identification of plant species best adapted for the uptake, sequestration, or degradation of specific contaminants, and evaluate these species in controlled greenhouse and field experiments

This section presents an overview of topics broadly related to phytoremediation that identify plant species best adapted for the uptake, sequestration, or degradation of specific contaminants, and evaluate these species in controlled greenhouse and field experiments

Figure 4.1: Sampled sites and concentration levels by date.

Figure 4.2: Heavy metal concentration levels at various spacing.

General theory and practical perception of science of plants enunciates correlational that lesser the plant species spacing, the slower the morphology in leaves, stems, or heights; indicated in this trial spacing of the 1 m x 1 m divan. The effects are due to the fact that when the plot sizes are smaller the plants are overcrowded thus, competition for limited nutrients is high. Also, there are deficiencies in certain metal concentration levels resulting in less biomass conversion in the plants. Comparatively, it is evident and true that the 4 m x 4 m spacing reflected vigorous plant growth.

The trials from observation showed stunted growth due to up take of high metal concentration levels over the trials period especially towards the end of trials life. From the raw data analysis and data manipulation indicated high concentrations levels in Zinc and Lead compared to the other species trailed out due to the type of growth media, reactively characteristics and weather conditions. The high levels of concentration trails did influence morphological features of species especially with the stems lengths and leave number sets over time respectively. The changes in development and growth in plants were outcomes of interaction and influences by the predominant weather conditions, growth medium, soil chemistry and plants ability to withstand different conditions presented thus the results in general.

Spacing and high concentration levels and their interactions had influence over the morphological features of plants with respect to few stunted growths that were experienced, and could be associated with contributions from other influential factors, and heavy toxic metal concentration levels for vigorous growth and development in the plant species. However, Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.4 from this trial indicated good performance in the 1 m x 1 m, 3 m x 3 m and 4 m x 4 m spacing, but showed decline in the 2 m x 2 m spacing.

Figure 4.3: Leaves and stem changes in relation to plot sizes over time.

Out of curiosity, observation of the species morphology over the stretch of time between February to October 2019 (Figure 4.3, with different plant spacing) indicated high roots and leaves settings at the early stage when the sediment plots still had moisture content, or were still in their aqueous-laden form. Later then, these species struggled in their leaves settings and stem lengths from the months of May to July and then again in September, and eventually started decreasing and eventually diminished towards November and December of 2019.

The root and leaves setting all grew well in the months of January and February, August and October. These were the months that experienced rainfalls in the area, thus, the growth rates and settings as displayed in Figure 4.3. It was also significant to see the plant species doing

very well in the rainy periods; as this is due to the rain's ability to neutralize the soils, reduce heat and reactions and to instigate vigorous growth and development.

The main factors that influences the growth and survival rates in terms of morphology of species where mostly associated with the growth medium from which the plants were growing from in the plots, chemistry in terms of different interactions and reactions due to their different characteristics and concentration levels, weather conditions influenced morphology through wet and dry patterns and periods along with the plants natural ability to adapt to different influential conditions presented before them.

Stunted growth was an effect of plant species deficiency to certain sufficient quantity and quality for normal growth and development given the influence from one or all of the conditions discussed here. The leaves number sets and stem lengths were also subjected to different conditions mentioned here along with spacing and nutrients competition for survival and growth. Less intact of certain elements illustrated with roots wilting, leaves fall offs and stunted growth. However even though the given influential conditions, the stem lengths stood firm and maintained strong struggle against the different influential factors.

Generally, the concentration levels of heavy metals were found to be high from the beginning to the end of the trials as indicated by the deceased trend of performances by the plant species compared to the guard rows that were doing very well alongside the trial plots within the set time period. Thus, it is evident of high levels of metals content in the plots that had influence over the morphological aspects of the plant species. From Figures 4.3, 4.4, 4.5, and 4.6, it is observed that increased stem lengths developments occurred in the first quarter and declined and steadily transits into September, then dropped in October and started picking up again towards the end of the year. The trend of repetitive fluctuation is dependent mostly on the weather pattern, moisture content and dry periods, as monitored over specific time periods. There is a tendency that when all heavy metals are combined and the concentrations are high over time, the plants do not seem capable of withstanding the heat levels imposed by the heavy concentrated levels in the sediments thus, the high mortality and stunted growth rates, and plant species such as *Typha* and *White Clover*, that seemed to even do well over the trial set period eventually died after a longer term due to struggle with the metal concentration levels. There are suggested ways to sustain plant growth with respect to dilution strategies to the metal concentration levels, and will be employed at a later time in a new study.

Figure 4.4: Species morphology against spacing and species type.

The outcome of the trials showed that higher level of concentration of metals uptake at wider plant spacing showed stunted progression in terms of plant species morphology. This is due to high heavy metals interaction from the combination of metals which had negative impacts and effects on the overall morphology of the plant species, as observed especially from the spacing monitored and indicated in Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.4. The trials that ran through the months (ranging from Feb – October of 2019), indicated high leaves settings and stem lengths with better results obtained in the months of February, August and October compared to the other months that trailed along. The results of certain morphological changes were due to rainfall and wet season's experiences, but later all species' leaves declined and experienced stunted growths due to lack of nutrients in the tailing sediments and less colonisation and interaction with the other surrounding species given the restriction demonstrated by the sediments.

Figures 4.5: Array of stem lengths of all species

Spacing influences plants' growth and morphological changes, as such, the arrays of stems and leaves indicated in Figures 4.5 and Figure 4.6 for plant species' physical morphology over the monitoring period.

The raw data analysis demonstrated struggles in growth generally however trema illustrated reasonable performance initially then lost leaves from wilting due to the stems inability to hold leaves enforced by different climatic patterns, soil chemistry and the plants inability to withstand adverse conditions. Most of the changes in the species trailed out were influenced by the different conditions especially by the growth medium, weather, soil chemistry and the plants natural abilities to withstand different hostile conditions.

Competition for nutrients at different spacing had greater effects on morphology of species trailed out. The sediment from tailings presented less plants-based nutrients thus the struggle and decline in growth and development amongst the plant species compared to the 4m x 4m spacing with sufficient space to stretch out for nutrients as indicated in their overall performance over time against different conditions mentioned.

From the general observation and raw data analysis indicated that copper concentration showed less impact on the plant species morphology but combined with other metals showed different changes given interactive and influential results over time.

Even though the concentrations and reactivity in the soil chemistry and growth media, rainfall assisted ease the situation with moisturise soil conditions and reduced interaction and reactions of different heavy metal concentrations however the dry periods intervene with reduction in plant growth and development over the trial periods especially toward the end of trials Generally, copper indicated from predication that it had less impact and influence on morphology of the trailed plant species over different conditional demonstrations.

Figure 4.6: Array of leaf numbers of plant species.

The trends from the figures indicate gradual inclines, however, struggled over time given the growth medium of sediments with insufficient supply and competition for the limited nutrients availability. The monitoring noted overall average stem lengths and leave numbers ranging from 5 – 60 mm and 1 - 16 leaf sets, respectively, during the monitoring period. Leaves and stem in this trial were good indicators of the plants survival and adaptation rates as noted throughout the trials.

4.3. Elucidation of the physical, chemical, physiological and metabolic mechanisms of contaminant uptake, translocation, sequestration/detoxification, partitioning, and bioaccumulation in phytoremediation plants

Figure 4.7: Plant species growth and survival rate.

The weekly observation and monitoring in Figure 4.7 indicated good performances by white clover, typha, tephrosia and lupin compared to the other species that trailed along over the weekly monitoring periods in different months of the calendar year. Table 4.1 lists the 7 plant species trailed in the tailing storage plots at different spacings. The plant species were chosen because of their characteristics and adaptability to grow and predominantly colonise with other secondary species in cleared and disturbed areas, and around the tailings vicinity from mining activities. These selected species are the primary colonizers and are predominant especially in the upper montane areas. The selected species are shrubs, flowers and secondary species that are used as part of the rehabilitation program on the mine disturbed areas. The plant species were trailed out in different plots in different spacing ranging from 1 m x 1 m spacing to 4 m x 4 m to see their growth rates and changes in their growth habits in heavy concentrated heavy metal contained sediments. The predominant secondary plant species in the area are shrubs and leguminous plants, especially lupin (*Lupinus maxicanus*) and Tephrosia (*Tephrosia vogelii*). The growth and behaviour of these two species are seen as indicators of plant growth and or decease of plants due to certain growth media and environmental conditions available over time. The main indication shows that white clover, typha and lupin did moderately well in all plots and in all different plant spacing, whilst tephrosia seemed to show eventual struggle

given the high levels of concentration of metals, soil chemistry, and meteorology along with other factors of concern that are unknown parameters not monitored and tested.

Figure 4.7 illustrated their different growth rates and stem length changes in different graphical settings over time and periods in real time investigations. All the species performed exceptionally well in their growths and stem lengths. The spacing of 2 m x 2 m seemed to trail back in growth and stem lengths (Figure 4.3). The overall morphological changes are direct effects from weather, metal concentration, and the growth media applied on them. The other plants did grow well at spacings, especially, the 1 m x 1 m spacing and 3 m x 3 m spacing followed by the 4 m x 4 m in the initial planting and monitoring records, however, growth trends declined in the late months of 2019 due to lack of moisture and reactions imposed on the plants by the heavy metal concentration mostly due to the heat levels during the summer period.

Generally the Typha (*Typha latifolia*) and white clover (*Trifolium repens*) performed very well over time but the white clover population eventually declined and diminished given the high concentration levels, compared to Typha which managed to withstand the conductions but most of the leaves turned yellowish and eventually the leaves became brown as indication of internal heat and stress from the high combination of heavy metals and reactions in the plots. In general, all did well but later all wilted and turned black and diminished. However, there were some grass species that invaded the plots and did very well (which data was collected of them as illustrated in Appendix I).

Fig 4.7 illustrates the percentage of growth and survival distribution of the plant species population (Table 4.1) in each of the trial plots over the set time period. It was indicative that the Homalantus (*Homalantus arfakiensis*), Kikuyu (*Penisetum clandestinum*) experienced high mortality rates in the plots compared to trailing survival and growth rates demonstrated by Lupin (*Lupin maxicanus*) at 42%, Tephrosia (*Tephrosia vogelii*) at 50% with white clover (*Trifolium repens*) at 100 % followed by Typha (*Typha latifolia*) at 60%, respectively. The trended survival and growth rates are directly proportional to the heavy metal concentration levels (heat) as physically seen and understood during the trials and monitoring over the time stretch. Few managed to recover from the rainy seasons, but eventually most died by end of trials in general.

Regardless of the heavy metal concentration, two species *Typha* and *White clover*, did better, and indicate that both of these plants can withstand and accommodate various concentration levels of heavy metals in their body parts especially in the leaves and stem as indicators of their morphological changes shown in Figure 4.7. Furthermore, plant species like White Clover, *Typha*, and to some degree White Tephrosia and Lupin can withstand high levels of metal concentration, and can be further studied and researched for better and in-depth results in their utilisation for phytoremediation in tailings storage facilities in the mining industries.

4.4. Demonstration of plant-based clean up systems for heavy metals, radionuclides and organics are low-cost, low-tech, environmentally-friendly, and economical at actual contaminated sites

Figure 4.8: Copper concentration levels against stem length development.

The heavy metal concentration levels were somewhat directly proportional to plant morphology as observed; the higher the concentration levels, the lesser the leaves and stem development in the species, with examples indicated in Figures 4.8, 4.9 and 4.10 with plant species development and transformation through the length of concentration levels imposed on the plants.

Figure 4.9: Plant species morphology over Nickel and Lead concentrations.

Plant species observed over concentration levels, for example, of copper, and zinc over time against stem lengths and leaves development indicated proportional and reflective performances, as in Figures 4.8 and 4.10, respectively. The cases for copper and zinc indicated higher levels of stem length and leaves settings and development, compared to the other heavy metal concentration levels. For the case of copper, cadmium (not shown), and zinc, good performance of leaves and stem lengths were observed in this trial.

Figure 4.10: Plant species morphology over Zinc concentration

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSIONS

The use of plants as vegetation cover for mine disturbed areas, known as phytoremediation of disturbed land contaminated by heavily concentrated heavy metals, does seem to have considerable potential. There are numerous evidences from the predominant natural establishment, and succession and colonisation of primary and secondary plant species on contaminated sites that several plant species can survive and withstand adverse conditions and grow to stabilize disturbed land. Endurance appear to be because of facultative resilience which the aversion by foundations of profoundly polluted substrates or by immobilization of metals in root. There are evidences that tolerance maybe increased by acclimation of individuals.

The Standard deviation (Table 4.1 and 4.2 and Figure 4.1) of metals indicated high level of lead, followed by zinc and nickel, and the rest with a trend that indicated less level in the sediment over the period of observation. The trend of growth and development of plants showed stunted and mortality rates related to high accumulation of heavy metals in the plant tissues especially in the leaves and stems. The influential factor of concern on the fluctuations in the concentration levels are the weather interaction with plant growth, and uptake of heavy metals and changes in soil chemistry from different conditions and changes.

Phytoremediation identified plant species that are suitable for the uptake, sequestration, or degradation of specific contaminants, and evaluate these species in controlled greenhouse and field experiments (Fig. 4.2). General theory and practical perception of the science of plants enunciates correlational indication that the smaller the plant species spacing, the slower the progressive growth in terms of changes in leaves, stems, or heights; indicated in this trial spacing of the 1 m x 1 m plot. The effects are due to the fact that when the plot sizes are smaller the plants are overcrowded thus, competition for limited nutrients is high. Also, there are deficiencies in certain metal concentration levels resulting in conversion of less biomass in the plants. Comparatively, it is evident and true that the 4 m x 4 m spacing reflected vigorous plant growth. This observation indicated stunted growth due to up take of high metal concentration levels over the trials period especially towards the end of trials life.

Raw data analysis and data manipulation indicated high concentrations levels were noted from Zinc and Lead compared to the other species trailed out due to the type of growth media, reactively characteristics and weather conditions that instigated high concentration. The high

levels of concentration trails did influence morphological features of species especially with the stems lengths and leave number sets over time respectively. The changes in development and growth in plants were outcomes of interaction and influences by the predominant weather conditions, growth medium, soil chemistry and plants ability to withstand different conditions presented thus the results in general.

Generally, spacing had influence over the morphological features of plants with respect to few stunted growths that were experienced, and could be associated with contributions from other influential factors, and heavy toxic metal concentration levels for vigorous growth and development in the plant species. However, Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.4 from this trial indicated good performance in the 1 m x 1 m, 3 m x 3 m and 4 m x 4 m spacing, but showed decline in the 2 m x 2 m spacing.

Out of curiosity, observation of the species morphology over the stretch of time between February to October 2019 (Figure 4.3, with different plant spacing) indicated high roots and leaves settings at the early stage when the sediment plots still had moisture content, or were still in their aqueous-laden form. Later then, these species struggled in their leaves settings and stem lengths from the months of May to July and then again in September, and eventually started decreasing and eventually diminished towards November and December of 2019. It was also significant to see the plant species doing very well in the rainy periods; as this is due to the rain's ability to neutralize the soils, reduce heat and reactions and to instigate vigorous growth and development.

The main factors that influences the growth and survival rates in terms of morphology of species where mostly associated with the growth medium from which the plants were growing from in the plots, chemistry in terms of different interactions and reactions due to their different characteristics and concentration levels, weather conditions influenced morphology through wet and dry patterns and periods along with the plants natural ability to adapt to different influential conditions presented before them.

Stunted growth was an effect of plant species deficiency to certain sufficient quantity and quality for normal growth and development given the influence from one or all of the conditions discussed here. The leaves number sets and stem lengths were also subjected to different conditions mentioned here along with spacing and nutrients competition for survival

and growth. Less intact of certain elements illustrated with roots wilting, leaves fall off and stunted growth. However even though the given influential conditions, the stem lengths stood firm and maintained strong struggle against the different influential factors.

Even though the concentrations and reactivity in the soil chemistry and growth media, rainfall assisted ease the situation with moisten soil conditions and reduced interaction and reactions of different heavy metal concentrations however the dry periods intervene with reduction in plant growth and development over the trial periods especially toward the end of trials. Generally, copper indicated from predication that it had less impact and influence on morphology of the trailed plant species over different conditional demonstrations.

The figures trends indicated gradual inclines, however, struggled over time given the growth medium of sediments with insufficient supply and competition for the limited nutrients availability. The monitoring noted overall average stem lengths and leaf numbers ranging from 5 – 60 mm and 1 - 16 leaf sets, respectively, during the monitoring period. Leaves and stem in this trial were good indicators of the plants survival and adaptation rates as noted throughout the trials.

The weekly observation and monitoring indicated good performances by white clover, typha, tephrosia and lupin (Fig 4.7) compared to the other species that trailed along over the weekly monitoring periods in different months of the calendar year. The plant species (Tab 4.) were chosen because of their characteristics and adaptability to grow and predominantly colonise with other secondary species in cleared and disturbed areas, and around the tailings vicinity from mining activities. These selected species are the primary colonizers and are predominant especially in the upper montane areas. The selected species are shrubs, flowers and secondary species that are used as part of the rehabilitation program on the mine disturbed areas. The plant species were trailed out in different plots in different spacing ranging from 1 m x 1 m spacing to 4 m x 4 m to see their growth rates and changes in their growth habits in heavy concentrated heavy metal contained sediments. The predominant secondary plant species in the area are shrubs and leguminous plants, especially lupin (*Lupinus maxicanus*) and Tephrosia (*Tephrosia vogelii*). The growth and behaviour of these two species are seen as indicators of plant growth and or decease of plants due to certain growth media and environmental conditions available over time. The main indication shows that white clover, typha and lupin

did moderately well in all plots and in all different plant spacing, whilst tephrosia seemed to show eventual struggle given the high levels of concentration of metals, soil chemistry, and meteorology along with other factors of concern that are unknown parameters not monitored and tested.

Figure 4.7 illustrated their different growth rates and stem length changes in different graphical settings over time and periods in real time investigations. All the species performed exceptionally well in their growths and stem lengths. The spacing of 2 m x 2 m seemed to trail back in growth and stem lengths (Figure 4.3). The overall morphological changes are direct effects from weather, metal concentration, and the growth media applied on them. The other plants did grow well at spacings, especially, the 1 m x 1 m spacing and 3 m x 3 m spacing followed by the 4 m x 4 m in the initial planting and monitoring records, however, growth trends declined in the late months of 2019 due to lack of moisture and reactions imposed on the plants by the heavy metal concentration mostly due to the heat levels during the summer period.

Typha (*Typha latifolia*) and white clover (*Trifolium repens*) performed very well over time however white clover population eventually declined and diminished given the high concentration levels, compared to Typha which managed to withstand the conductions but most of the leaves turned yellowish and eventually the leaves became brown as indication of internal heat and stress from the high combination of heavy metals and reactions in the plots. In general, all did well but later all wilted and turned black and diminished. However, there were some grass species that invaded the plots and did very well (which data was collected of them as illustrated in Appendix I).

Percentage of growth and survival distribution of the plant species population (Table 4.1 & Fig 4.7) in each of the trial plots over the set time period. It was indicative that the Homalantus (*Homalantus arfakiensis*), Kikuyu (*Penisetum clandestinum*) experienced high mortality rates in the plots compared to trailing survival and growth rates demonstrated by Lupin (*Lupin maxicanus*) at 42%, Tephrosia (*Tephrosia vogelii*) at 50% with white clover (*Trifolium repens*) at 100 % followed by Typha (*Typha latifolia*) at 60%, respectively. The trended survival and growth rates are directly proportional to the heavy metal concentration levels (heat) as physically seen and understood during the trials and monitoring over the time stretch.

Few managed to recover from the rainy seasons, but eventually most died by end of trials in general.

Regardless of the heavy metal concentration, two species Typha and White clover, did better, and indicate that both of these plants can withstand and accommodate various concentration levels of heavy metals in their body parts especially in the leaves and stem as indicators of their morphological changes shown in Figure 4.7. Furthermore, plant species like White Clover, Typha, and to some degree White Tephrosia and Lupin can withstand high levels of metal concentration, and can be further studied and researched for better and in-depth results in their utilisation for phytoremediation in tailings storage facilities in the mining industries.

The heavy metal concentration levels were somewhat directly proportional to plant morphology as observed; the higher the concentration levels, the lesser the leaves and stem development in the species, with examples indicated in Figures 4.8, 4.9 and 4.10 with plant species development and transformation through the length of concentration levels imposed on the plants.

Plant species observed over concentration levels, for example, of copper, and zinc over time against stem lengths and leaves development indicated proportional and reflective performances, as in Figures 4.8 and 4.10, respectively. The cases for copper and zinc indicated higher levels of stem length and leaves settings and development, compared to the other heavy metal concentration levels. For the case of copper, cadmium (not shown), and zinc, good performance of leaves and stem lengths were observed in this trial.

The study indicated high mortality rates from homalantus, kikuyu, trema and lupin, compared with struggle and survival rates demonstrated by Typha, White Clover and Tephrosia in the high concentrated tailing stored plots.

There were metals that were not too concentrated, for example zinc, copper and cadmium, whilst lead and nickel were highly concentrated, and so plants did not seem to tolerate their presence in large quantities.

The Tailing Storage Facility Soil Concentration levels of all the soil parameters for metals in illustrated 100% concentration levels (Fig 4.2) of all the heavy metal parameters from the fresh sediments collected from the Tailing Facility and analysed for concentration levels.

The trends of growth and development of plants had a direction relationship or proportion to the struggle, and stunted and mortality rate reflective of high concentration levels (as accumulation) of heavy metals in the plant species tissues especially in the leaves and stems. The influence factor of concern with the fluctuations in the concentration levels lied with weather, interaction with the plant growth, uptake of heavy metals, and the changes in soil chemistry from different conditions and changes. The changes in the soil concentration levels in relation to plant morphology, meteorology and soil chemistry depends on the plants ability to withstand the concentration levels, metal uptake, and changes in their features and concentration levels as indicated in the daily random analysis in the month.

Phytoremediation has many advantageous features and characteristics that make it an appropriate and successful technology, giving practitioners a choice and valuable options for remediation. It had major advantages such as low cost and minimal engineering cost with effective vegetation cover, soil stabilisation, and reducing spread of contaminants. Collaboration with universities, research institutes and government bodies could create the multidisciplinary teams necessary to address issues such as; the agronomic practices needed for successful establishment of vegetation; development of plants for specific remediation requirements; the question of what constitutes 'clean-up' (bioavailable vs. total); effects of growing plants on the wider environment; and fate and disposal of high metal biomass. There is still a lot of crucial and applied exploration expected to support phytoremediation innovation.

CHAPTER 6: RECOMMENDATIONS

Heavy metals uptake via way of means of flowers the usage of phytoremediation generation appears to be a wealthy manner to remediate heavy-metals-infected environment. It has a few blessings as compared with different typically used traditional technologies. Several factors must be considered in order to accomplish a high-performance remediation result. The maximum vital issue is an appropriate plant species which may be used to uptake the contaminant. Even though the phytoremediation technique seems to be one of the best alternatives, it also has some limitations. Prolonged studies wishes to be performed to decrease this hindrance as a way to observe this approach effectively.

The study undertaken for this thesis was important as it revealed the kind of benefits or short falls generated for the Ok Tedi project, and so for other mining industries. Phytoremediation will show the kind of impact, extent, and views people affected by the mine will have on the mining operation.

The considerable benefit streams made by the Ok Tedi Mine project will act as major stimuli for development in the project areas, in Western Province and Papua New Guinea as a whole. The benefit streams have the potential both to improve the discharges of heavy and toxic metal tailings, particularly in in the mining and community ecosystems through phytoremediation and through such biological means which could be efficient at less cost through an environmentally-friendly approach. With the outcome from this study, White Clover, Typha and Tephrosia are hyper accumulating plants which can withstand high quantity of heavy metal contained in their different plant structures as biomass, and also at some degree these species detoxicate the soil of the toxic heavy metals, by absorbing, stabilizing, and accumulating the heavy metals in its different plant structures; roots, stem, and leaves. Therefore, these species are suitable for phytoremediation and rehabilitation process of the vegetation in the mined sites in the country.

It is imperative to state that there has to be more trials and collaborative research in phytoremediation with bigger organisations like the mines and higher institutions, and make funding allocations and research and laboratory analyses available for plants and soils to be analysed so information obtained shall assist with implementation of low-cost

phytoremediation works from the research findings, combined with more support from the government and vocal institutions in environmental management.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX I: Images of Trials

TSF Sediments	Collection of TSF Sediments	Plots and Sediments into beds
Plot Preparation	TSF Material Beds	Prepared for Planting
Planting of <i>Tephrosia</i>	Planted Beds	Sample plots of <i>Homalantus Spp.</i>
Planted plot with TSF	Kikuyu Performance TS Materials	Performance - Invaded Grass species

APPENDIX II: Soil Parameters_ Raw Data Used in Analysis

16/5/19				16/5/19				16/5/19				16/5/19				16/5/19				16/5/19				16/5/19				16/5/19				16/5/19				16/5/19				16/5/19				16/5/19				16/5/19				16/5/19				16/5/19				16/5/19				16/5/19				16/5/19			
Date	Week	Month	Time	Sample ID	Mercury (g/kg)	Nickel (g/kg)	Lead (g/kg)	Copper Available (mg/kg)	Chromium (g/kg)	Ni (g/kg)	Cadmium (g/kg)	Zinc Available (mg/kg)	Date	Week	Month	Time	Sample ID	Mercury (g/kg)	Nickel (g/kg)	Lead (g/kg)	Copper Available (mg/kg)	Chromium (g/kg)	Ni (g/kg)	Cadmium (g/kg)	Zinc Available (mg/kg)	Date	Week	Month	Time	Sample ID	Mercury (g/kg)	Nickel (g/kg)	Lead (g/kg)	Copper Available (mg/kg)	Chromium (g/kg)	Ni (g/kg)	Cadmium (g/kg)	Zinc Available (mg/kg)	Date	Week	Month	Time	Sample ID	Mercury (g/kg)	Nickel (g/kg)	Lead (g/kg)	Copper Available (mg/kg)	Chromium (g/kg)	Ni (g/kg)	Cadmium (g/kg)	Zinc Available (mg/kg)																				
16/5/19	1	May	12:31	SN-S09	0.00017	0.028	0.041	4.4	0.00018	0.01	2	0.00017	1	May	9:45	SN-S05	0.000001	0.035	0.02	1	0.000156	0.01	1.4	0.000001	1	May	9:45	SN-S06	0.000021	0.034	0.031	0.1	0.000136	0.01	0.3	0.000021	1	May	9:45	SN-S06	0.000021	0.034	0.031	0.1	0.000136	0.01	0.3	0.000021																							
16/5/19	1	May	12:15	SN-S08	0.000003	0.035	0.028	0.8	0.000161	0.01	1.3	0.000003	1	May	9:30	SN-S03	0.00012	0.027	0.029	0.2	0.000142	0.01	0.6	0.00012	1	May	9:30	SN-S04	0.000019	0.03	0.03	0.9	0.000172	0.01	1.4	0.000019	1	May	9:30	SN-S04	0.000019	0.03	0.03	0.9	0.000172	0.01	1.4	0.000019																							
16/5/19	1	May	12:15	SN-S07	0.000026	0.033	0.033	0.9	0.00013	0.01	1.4	0.000026	1	May	9:30	SN-S03	0.00012	0.027	0.029	0.2	0.000142	0.01	0.6	0.00012	1	May	9:30	SN-S04	0.000019	0.03	0.03	0.9	0.000172	0.01	1.4	0.000019	1	May	9:30	SN-S04	0.000019	0.03	0.03	0.9	0.000172	0.01	1.4	0.000019																							
16/5/19	1	May	15:30	SN-S01	0.000001	0.028	0.032	0.1	0.00001	0.11	0.3	0.000001	1	May	15:30	SN-S02	0.0001	0.03	0.034	0.2	0.000086	0.41	0.5	0.0001	1	May	15:30	SN-S02	0.0001	0.03	0.034	0.2	0.000086	0.41	0.5	0.0001	1	May	15:30	SN-S02	0.0001	0.03	0.034	0.2	0.000086	0.41	0.5	0.0001																							

16/7/19	16/7/19	16/7/19	16/7/19	16/7/19	16/7/19	16/7/19	16/7/19	16/7/19	16/7/19	16/7/19	16/7/19	16/7/19	16/5/19	16/5/19	16/5/19	16/5/19	16/5/19
2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1
Jul	May	May	May	May	May												
13:30	14:00	14:00	14:00	14:30	14:30	14:30	14:30	14:51	14:51	14:51	14:51	14:15	14:15	14:15	14:15	13:06	13:06
SN-S21	SN-S20	SN-S19	SN-S18	SN-S17	SN-S16	SN-S15	SN-S14	SN-S13	SN-S12	SN-S11	SN-S10						
0.00027	0.00067	0.00031	0.00036	0.00053	0.00029	0.00001	0.00078	0.00078	0.00078	0.00078	0.00012	0.00014	0.00078	0.00001	0.00014	0.00012	0.00012
0.032	0.032	0.034	0.023	0.032	0.036	0.026	0.025	0.034	0.032	0.029	0.032	0.032	0.034	0.029	0.032	0.032	0.032
0.032	0.037	0.022	0.027	0.039	0.03	0.027	0.04	0.036	0.03	0.031	0.038	0.03	0.036	0.031	0.03	0.038	0.038
1.1	1.1	1.6	0.7	0.7	3	2.7	5	4.4	2.6	2.5	3.7	2.6	4.4	2.5	2.6	3.7	3.7
0.000032	0.000037	0.000059	0.000064	0.000173	0.000255	0.000314	0.000272	0.000229	0.000234	0.000212	0.000202	0.000234	0.000229	0.000212	0.000234	0.000202	0.000202
0.06	0.05	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01
1.2	0.5	1.5	0.9	0.8	2.9	3	1.1	1.1	0.5	0.5	1.7	0.5	1.1	0.5	0.5	1.7	1.7
0.00027	0.00067	0.00031	0.00036	0.00053	0.00029	0.00001	0.00078	0.00078	0.00014	0.00001	0.00012	0.00014	0.00078	0.00001	0.00014	0.00012	0.00012

2/10/19	2/10/19	2/10/19	2/10/19	23/9/19	23/9/19	23/9/19	23/9/19	23/9/19	23/9/19	23/9/19	23/9/19
ω	ω	ω	ω	ω	ω	ω	ω	ω	ω	ω	ω
Oct	Oct	Oct	Sep	Sep	Sep	Sep	Sep	Sep	Sep	Sep	Sep
12:30	12:30	14:00	14:00	14:18	14:18	12:45	12:45	12:30	12:30	12:30	14:04
SN-S45	SN-S44	SN-S43	SN-S42	SN-S41	SN-S40	SN-S39	SN-S38	SN-S37	SN-S36	SN-S35	SN-S34
0.00001	0.00018	0.00026	0.00029	0.00012	0.00013	0.00018	0.00001	0.00001	0.00001	0.00023	0.00001
0.033	0.025	0.031	0.027	0.035	0.027	0.028	0.032	0.034	0.021	0.025	0.029
0.017	0.025	0.024	0.023	0.022	0.023	0.032	0.031	0.038	0.024	0.024	0.032
0.01	0.7	0.9	0.3	0.2	0.4	1.3	2.7	2.2	0.7	0.7	1
0.000027	0.000032	0.000027	0.000027	0.000065	0.00012	0.000207	0.000263	0.000224	0.000147	0.000115	0.000153
0.06	0.07	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.08	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
0.2	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.3	2.1	4.2	2.1	2.1	0.4	0.4	0.7
0.00001	0.00018	0.00026	0.00029	0.00012	0.00013	0.00018	0.00001	0.00001	0.00001	0.00023	0.00001

		2/10/19	2/10/19	2/10/19	2/10/19	2/10/19	2/10/19	2/10/19	2/10/19	2/10/19	2/10/19	2/10/19	2/10/19
		4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
		Oct	Oct	Oct	Oct	Oct	Oct	Oct	Oct	Oct	Oct	Oct	Oct
		8:37	8:37	9:11	9:11	9:55	9:55	11:30	11:30	11:30	11:30	12:00	12:00
Min	Average	SN-S55	SN-S54	SN-S53	SN-S52	SN-S51	SN-S50	SN-S49	SN-S48	SN-S47	SN-S46		
0.000001	0.000148	0.00001	0.00001	0.00001	0.00001	0.00001	0.00023	0.00004	0.00009	0.00001	0.00089		
0.021	0.029	0.024	0.021	0.029	0.031	0.028	0.033	0.029	0.025	0.028	0.025	0.025	0.025
0.017	0.029	0.022	0.035	0.029	0.032	0.037	0.025	0.028	0.027	0.039	0.018		
0.01	1.13	0.2	0.2	0.7	0.4	0.6	0.4	0.8	0.8	0.6	0.01		
0.000001	0.000139	0.00035	0.000145	0.000164	0.000174	0.000153	0.000147	0.000087	0.000076	0.000027	0.000027		
0.01	0.050	0.04	0.03	0.11	0.1	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.08	0.11		
0.2	1.10	0.7	0.6	0.7	0.9	1.1	1.2	1.5	3.7	3.5	0.2		
0.000001	0.000148	0.00001	0.00001	0.00001	0.00001	0.00001	0.00023	0.00004	0.00009	0.00001	0.00089		

APPENDIX III: Letter of Confirmation on Practical/Experimental Component of Thesis

HEAD OFFICE: Phone: +649 3000.

1 Dakon Road, Tabubil, Western Province, 332, Papua New Guinea

To: The Department of Civil Engineering – University of Technology, Lae Morobe Province.

Cc: Nathaniel Dasyal – Mining Waste Management

Date: 19th of May 2020

Subject: Letter of Confirmation for Study of Phytoremediation Studies

Nathaniel Dasyal had shown interest in studies around Phytoremediation whilst the plans for mine closure planning aspect of the Tailing Storage Facility caught up with the Mining.

As such he had self-sponsored himself to take up this studies out of curiosity to understand the behaviours of the Plant Species in Heavy Metal Concentrated Sediments.

The study was basically done by this mine to assist with the plants ability to withstand the adverse metal concentration levels and mostly importantly to identify plants species that can do well in these conditions so can be recommended for rehabilitation should the mine close or if the facility fills to the brim and is to relocate to another site.

Since he was also heading the section, we have allowed him to undertake the studies and to assist the mine with the necessary field raw data to still appropriately informed decision in the life of mine.

Should you have any queries, please do not hesitate to contact Manager Mine Waste Management here at Ok Tedi Mining Limited.

Yours faithfully

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'H. Min', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Hendrick Min - Manager Mine Waste Management Ok Tedi Mining Limited.